

Perceptual Affects of Flow Assignments

We, as perceivers and imaginers, have all manner of effects on that underpinning of reality we call, "substance." Be it substance of spoken meaning or substance of ascertained actuality of existant things, how we perceive something drastically imparts variations of meaning, significance and import. In fact, as we will show, those very fabricated dimensions may instill substance, instill meaning, and drive emotions, ideal emotions, imparting information into the fabric of reality through the perception itself. Through the data we put in, we can effect the words we read, the words of the written reality, the tantras of the allegedly meaning – based derivations, and the formal fundamental principles of all existence as they evolve in the environment.

**This is the mathematics of how these things may transpire,
and the dynamics of these flow forms are indicative of emotions in a machine.**

$$\theta r = \gamma x - \alpha y \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{0.0.1.} \quad \theta r = s$$

$$\mathbf{0.0.2.} \quad \gamma x = q$$

$$\mathbf{0.0.3.} \quad \alpha y = p$$

$$\mathbf{0.0.4.} \quad l \alpha = w$$

$$l n[\cdot] = y^2 = l^2 - h^2 \quad (2)$$

$$\theta r = \gamma x - \alpha \sqrt{l^2 - h^2} \quad (3)$$

$$s = q - \alpha \sqrt{l^2 - h^2} \quad (4)$$

$$\blacksquare l \sin[\beta] = h$$

$$\blacksquare \text{SOH; } h/l = \sin[\beta]$$

$$\blacksquare \text{CAH; } y/l = \cos[\beta]$$

$$\blacksquare \text{TOA; } h/y = \tan[\beta]$$

$$y = \frac{q - s}{\alpha} \quad (5)$$

Consider how the variable, w, is purely algebraic – it exists as a construct of algebraic symbolic manipulation, alone and has no actual reality within the diagrammed geometry, which is postulated real through a perfect calculus of balanced infinity forms. It is therefore called a, "fabricated," dimension. However, we will show that these kinds of fabricated dimensions are most useful for describing some of the most important phenomena that mankind has designated, "real."

Therefore, the imagination, or perhaps rather, the construct of man's imagination, determination and functional stipulation is a fundamental component of his perceived reality. In this way, empiricism can include the product of the subject while acknowledging the indeterminable and ineffectuality of absolutism.

Fabricated Dimension W and its functions

With the following forms, solutions to the compiled, or "made up," quantity, $l \alpha = w$, we demonstrate the varying functions of which w is:

1. Velocity of a Geometric Mean Time Unit Equals Instantaneous Velocity of the Height:

$$\text{In[]:= } D[D[D[D[\frac{\sqrt{-q^2 + 2qs - s^2 + w^2}}{\alpha}, q], s], w], \alpha]$$

$$\text{Out[]:= } -\frac{3(2q - 2s)(-2q + 2s)w}{4(-q^2 + 2qs - s^2 + w^2)^{5/2}\alpha^2} + \frac{w}{(-q^2 + 2qs - s^2 + w^2)^{3/2}\alpha^2}$$

$$\text{Geometric Mean Time} = \frac{(\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{2\pi};$$

$$\text{velocity} = \frac{\sqrt{-q^2 + 2qs - s^2 + w^2}}{\alpha (\text{Geometric Mean Time})} = \frac{2\pi \sqrt{-q^2 + 2qs - s^2 + w^2}}{\alpha (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}$$

$$\frac{2\pi \sqrt{-q^2 + 2qs - s^2 + w^2}}{\alpha (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}} == -\frac{3(2q - 2s)(-2q + 2s)w}{4(-q^2 + 2qs - s^2 + w^2)^{5/2}\alpha^2} + \frac{w}{(-q^2 + 2qs - s^2 + w^2)^{3/2}\alpha^2}$$

$$\text{In[]:= } \text{Solve[}$$

$$-\frac{3(2q - 2s)(-2q + 2s)w}{4(-q^2 + 2qs - s^2 + w^2)^{5/2}\alpha^2} + \frac{w}{(-q^2 + 2qs - s^2 + w^2)^{3/2}\alpha^2} == \frac{2\pi \sqrt{-q^2 + 2qs - s^2 + w^2}}{\alpha (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}, w]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Out[]} = & \left\{ \left\{ \mathbf{w} \rightarrow \text{Root} \left[2 \pi q^6 - 12 \pi q^5 s + 30 \pi q^4 s^2 - 40 \pi q^3 s^3 + 30 \pi q^2 s^4 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & 12 \pi q s^5 + 2 \pi s^6 + \left(\frac{2 q^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} - \frac{4 q s (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} + \frac{2 s^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} \right) \#1 + \\
 & (-6 \pi q^4 + 24 \pi q^3 s - 36 \pi q^2 s^2 + 24 \pi q s^3 - 6 \pi s^4) \#1^2 + \\
 & \left. \left. \frac{(\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3} \#1^3}{\alpha} + (6 \pi q^2 - 12 \pi q s + 6 \pi s^2) \#1^4 - 2 \pi \#1^6 \&, 1 \right] \right\}, \\
 & \left\{ \mathbf{w} \rightarrow \text{Root} \left[2 \pi q^6 - 12 \pi q^5 s + 30 \pi q^4 s^2 - 40 \pi q^3 s^3 + 30 \pi q^2 s^4 - 12 \pi q s^5 + \right. \right. \\
 & 2 \pi s^6 + \left(\frac{2 q^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} - \frac{4 q s (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} + \frac{2 s^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} \right) \#1 + \\
 & (-6 \pi q^4 + 24 \pi q^3 s - 36 \pi q^2 s^2 + 24 \pi q s^3 - 6 \pi s^4) \#1^2 + \\
 & \left. \left. \frac{(\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3} \#1^3}{\alpha} + (6 \pi q^2 - 12 \pi q s + 6 \pi s^2) \#1^4 - 2 \pi \#1^6 \&, 2 \right] \right\}, \\
 & \left\{ \mathbf{w} \rightarrow \text{Root} \left[2 \pi q^6 - 12 \pi q^5 s + 30 \pi q^4 s^2 - 40 \pi q^3 s^3 + 30 \pi q^2 s^4 - 12 \pi q s^5 + \right. \right. \\
 & 2 \pi s^6 + \left(\frac{2 q^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} - \frac{4 q s (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} + \frac{2 s^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} \right) \#1 + \\
 & (-6 \pi q^4 + 24 \pi q^3 s - 36 \pi q^2 s^2 + 24 \pi q s^3 - 6 \pi s^4) \#1^2 + \\
 & \left. \left. \frac{(\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3} \#1^3}{\alpha} + (6 \pi q^2 - 12 \pi q s + 6 \pi s^2) \#1^4 - 2 \pi \#1^6 \&, 3 \right] \right\}, \\
 & \left\{ \mathbf{w} \rightarrow \text{Root} \left[2 \pi q^6 - 12 \pi q^5 s + 30 \pi q^4 s^2 - 40 \pi q^3 s^3 + 30 \pi q^2 s^4 - 12 \pi q s^5 + \right. \right. \\
 & 2 \pi s^6 + \left(\frac{2 q^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} - \frac{4 q s (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} + \frac{2 s^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} \right) \#1 + \\
 & (-6 \pi q^4 + 24 \pi q^3 s - 36 \pi q^2 s^2 + 24 \pi q s^3 - 6 \pi s^4) \#1^2 + \\
 & \left. \left. \frac{(\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3} \#1^3}{\alpha} + (6 \pi q^2 - 12 \pi q s + 6 \pi s^2) \#1^4 - 2 \pi \#1^6 \&, 4 \right] \right\}, \\
 & \left\{ \mathbf{w} \rightarrow \text{Root} \left[2 \pi q^6 - 12 \pi q^5 s + 30 \pi q^4 s^2 - 40 \pi q^3 s^3 + 30 \pi q^2 s^4 - 12 \pi q s^5 + \right. \right. \\
 & 2 \pi s^6 + \left(\frac{2 q^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} - \frac{4 q s (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} + \frac{2 s^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} \right) \#1 + \\
 & (-6 \pi q^4 + 24 \pi q^3 s - 36 \pi q^2 s^2 + 24 \pi q s^3 - 6 \pi s^4) \#1^2 + \\
 & \left. \left. \frac{(\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3} \#1^3}{\alpha} + (6 \pi q^2 - 12 \pi q s + 6 \pi s^2) \#1^4 - 2 \pi \#1^6 \&, 5 \right] \right\}, \\
 & \left\{ \mathbf{w} \rightarrow \text{Root} \left[2 \pi q^6 - 12 \pi q^5 s + 30 \pi q^4 s^2 - 40 \pi q^3 s^3 + 30 \pi q^2 s^4 - 12 \pi q s^5 + \right. \right. \\
 & 2 \pi s^6 + \left(\frac{2 q^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} - \frac{4 q s (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} + \frac{2 s^2 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} \right) \#1 + \\
 & (-6 \pi q^4 + 24 \pi q^3 s - 36 \pi q^2 s^2 + 24 \pi q s^3 - 6 \pi s^4) \#1^2 + \\
 & \left. \left. \frac{(\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3} \#1^3}{\alpha} + (6 \pi q^2 - 12 \pi q s + 6 \pi s^2) \#1^4 - 2 \pi \#1^6 \&, 6 \right] \right\} \}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & w \text{ is a function of the fabricated form, Solve } \left[h == \frac{\sqrt{-q^2 + 2qs - s^2 + w^2}}{\alpha}, w \right] \\
 & \left\{ \left\{ w \rightarrow -\sqrt{q^2 - 2qs + s^2 + h^2 \alpha^2} \right\}, \left\{ w \rightarrow \sqrt{q^2 - 2qs + s^2 + h^2 \alpha^2} \right\} \right\} \\
 & w_* == l \alpha == \sqrt{q^2 - 2qs + s^2 + h^2 \alpha^2} = \sqrt{q^2 - 2qs + s^2 + m^2} \\
 & z_{**} == m_* - w_* == \sqrt{-q^2 + 2qs - s^2 + m^2} - \sqrt{q^2 - 2qs + s^2 + m^2} \\
 & \text{Solve} \left[m - w == \sqrt{-q^2 + 2qs - s^2 + (l \alpha)^2} - \sqrt{q^2 - 2qs + s^2 + h^2 \alpha^2}, w \right] \\
 & \left\{ \left\{ w \rightarrow \frac{q^2 \sqrt{m^2 + q^2 - 2qs + s^2} - 2qs \sqrt{m^2 + q^2 - 2qs + s^2} + s^2 \sqrt{m^2 + q^2 - 2qs + s^2}}{q^2 - 2qs + s^2} \right\} \right\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus, w is actually a function of a subsequent, fabricated dimensions, m and z, and delineated (drawn) dimensions q and s.

3. w is a function of q and s through the phenomenological velocity, embedded dimension:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{In[*]:=} & \text{Solve} \left[\sqrt{-c^2 w^2 + c^2 q^2 - 2c^2 s q + c^2 s^2 + c^2 w^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2} == \right. \\
 & \left. \sqrt{-1. \cdot w^2 + q^2 - 2. \cdot s q + s^2 + w^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2} v, w \right] \\
 \text{Out[*]:=} & \left\{ \left\{ w \rightarrow \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \frac{1. \sqrt{8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 - 1. q^2 v^2 + 2. q s v^2 - 1. s^2 v^2}}{\sqrt{8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}} \right. \\
 & \left. \right\}, \\
 & \left\{ w \rightarrow \right. \\
 & \left. \frac{\sqrt{8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 - 1. q^2 v^2 + 2. q s v^2 - 1. s^2 v^2}}{\sqrt{8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}} \right\} \left. \right\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Notable Quark Similarities of Delineated Dimensional Solutions

What we see here is six solutions that are tangibly, quarks. Cone – based quark geometries are actually a subset of this broader equation. This is fundamental to why and how our perception can transmute matter. W is a fabricated dimension, which from a flawless ordinal algorithmic calculus is dependent on the fully fabricated z dimensions. Thus, as our perceptual imagination yield generates patterns of fabricated dimensions, they can naturally modify the formulations of the very quarks of existential powers.

In[]:= Solve[

$$-\frac{3(2q-2s)(-2q+2s)w}{4(-q^2+2qs-s^2+w^2)^{5/2}\alpha^2} + \frac{w}{(-q^2+2qs-s^2+w^2)^{3/2}\alpha^2} == \frac{2\pi\sqrt{-q^2+2qs-s^2+w^2}}{\alpha(\alpha\gamma\theta)^{1/3}}, q]$$

$$\text{Out[]} = \left\{ \left\{ q \rightarrow \frac{1}{2} \left(2s - 2 \sqrt{\left(w^2 - \frac{2^{2/3} w (\alpha\gamma\theta)^{1/3}}{3^{1/3} \alpha \left(-\frac{27\pi^2 w^3 (\alpha\gamma\theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} + \frac{\sqrt{3} \sqrt{16\pi^3 w^3 \gamma\theta + 243\pi^4 w^6 (\alpha\gamma\theta)^{2/3}}}{\alpha} \right)^{1/3}} + \frac{\left(-\frac{27\pi^2 w^3 (\alpha\gamma\theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} + \frac{\sqrt{3} \sqrt{16\pi^3 w^3 \gamma\theta + 243\pi^4 w^6 (\alpha\gamma\theta)^{2/3}}}{\alpha} \right)^{1/3}}{6^{2/3} \pi} \right)} \right\}, \right.$$

$$\left. \left\{ q \rightarrow \frac{1}{2} \left(2s + 2 \sqrt{\left(w^2 - \frac{2^{2/3} w (\alpha\gamma\theta)^{1/3}}{3^{1/3} \alpha \left(-\frac{27\pi^2 w^3 (\alpha\gamma\theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} + \frac{\sqrt{3} \sqrt{16\pi^3 w^3 \gamma\theta + 243\pi^4 w^6 (\alpha\gamma\theta)^{2/3}}}{\alpha} \right)^{1/3}} + \frac{\left(-\frac{27\pi^2 w^3 (\alpha\gamma\theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} + \frac{\sqrt{3} \sqrt{16\pi^3 w^3 \gamma\theta + 243\pi^4 w^6 (\alpha\gamma\theta)^{2/3}}}{\alpha} \right)^{1/3}}{6^{2/3} \pi} \right)} \right\}, \right.$$

$$\left. \left\{ q \rightarrow \frac{1}{2} \left(2s - \sqrt{\left(4s^2 - 4 \left(\frac{\pi s^2 - \pi w^2}{\pi} - \frac{(1+i\sqrt{3}) w (\alpha\gamma\theta)^{1/3}}{6^{1/3} \alpha \left(-\frac{27\pi^2 w^3 (\alpha\gamma\theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} + \frac{\sqrt{3} \sqrt{16\pi^3 w^3 \gamma\theta + 243\pi^4 w^6 (\alpha\gamma\theta)^{2/3}}}{\alpha} \right)^{1/3}} + \frac{(1-i\sqrt{3}) \left(-\frac{27\pi^2 w^3 (\alpha\gamma\theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} + \frac{\sqrt{3} \sqrt{16\pi^3 w^3 \gamma\theta + 243\pi^4 w^6 (\alpha\gamma\theta)^{2/3}}}{\alpha} \right)^{1/3}}{2 \times 6^{2/3} \pi} \right)} \right)} \right\}, \right.$$

$$\left. \left\{ q \rightarrow \frac{1}{2} \left(2s + \sqrt{\left(4s^2 - 4 \left(\frac{\pi s^2 - \pi w^2}{\pi} - \frac{(1+i\sqrt{3}) w (\alpha\gamma\theta)^{1/3}}{6^{1/3} \alpha \left(-\frac{27\pi^2 w^3 (\alpha\gamma\theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} + \frac{\sqrt{3} \sqrt{16\pi^3 w^3 \gamma\theta + 243\pi^4 w^6 (\alpha\gamma\theta)^{2/3}}}{\alpha} \right)^{1/3}} + \frac{(1-i\sqrt{3}) \left(-\frac{27\pi^2 w^3 (\alpha\gamma\theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} + \frac{\sqrt{3} \sqrt{16\pi^3 w^3 \gamma\theta + 243\pi^4 w^6 (\alpha\gamma\theta)^{2/3}}}{\alpha} \right)^{1/3}}{2 \times 6^{2/3} \pi} \right)} \right)} \right\}, \right.$$

$$\left. \left\{ q \rightarrow \frac{1}{2} \left(2s - \sqrt{\left(4s^2 - 4 \left(\frac{\pi s^2 - \pi w^2}{\pi} - \frac{(1-i\sqrt{3}) w (\alpha\gamma\theta)^{1/3}}{6^{1/3} \alpha \left(-\frac{27\pi^2 w^3 (\alpha\gamma\theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} + \frac{\sqrt{3} \sqrt{16\pi^3 w^3 \gamma\theta + 243\pi^4 w^6 (\alpha\gamma\theta)^{2/3}}}{\alpha} \right)^{1/3}} + \frac{(1+i\sqrt{3}) \left(-\frac{27\pi^2 w^3 (\alpha\gamma\theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} + \frac{\sqrt{3} \sqrt{16\pi^3 w^3 \gamma\theta + 243\pi^4 w^6 (\alpha\gamma\theta)^{2/3}}}{\alpha} \right)^{1/3}}{2 \times 6^{2/3} \pi} \right)} \right)} \right\}, \right.$$

$$\left. \left. \left. \left. \frac{(1 + i \sqrt{3}) \left(-\frac{27 \pi^2 w^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} + \frac{\sqrt{3} \sqrt{16 \pi^3 w^3 \gamma \theta + 243 \pi^4 w^6 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}}{\alpha} \right)^{1/3}}{2 \times 6^{2/3} \pi} \right) \right) \right) \right\},$$

$$\left\{ \mathbf{q} \rightarrow \frac{1}{2} \left(2 \mathbf{s} + \sqrt{\left(4 \mathbf{s}^2 - 4 \left(\frac{\pi \mathbf{s}^2 - \pi w^2}{\pi} - \frac{(1 - i \sqrt{3}) w (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{6^{1/3} \alpha \left(-\frac{27 \pi^2 w^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} + \frac{\sqrt{3} \sqrt{16 \pi^3 w^3 \gamma \theta + 243 \pi^4 w^6 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}}{\alpha} \right)^{1/3}} \right)} \right)} \right. \right.$$

$$\left. \left. \left. \left. \frac{(1 + i \sqrt{3}) \left(-\frac{27 \pi^2 w^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} + \frac{\sqrt{3} \sqrt{16 \pi^3 w^3 \gamma \theta + 243 \pi^4 w^6 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}}{\alpha} \right)^{1/3}}{2 \times 6^{2/3} \pi} \right) \right) \right) \right\} \right\}$$

In[]:= Manipulate[SphericalPlot3D[

$$\left\{ \frac{1}{2} \left(2 \mathbf{s} - 2 \sqrt{\left(w^2 - \frac{2^{2/3} w (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{3^{1/3} \alpha \left(-\frac{27 \pi^2 w^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} + \frac{\sqrt{3} \sqrt{16 \pi^3 w^3 \gamma \theta + 243 \pi^4 w^6 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}}{\alpha} \right)^{1/3}} \right)} \right. \right.$$

$$\left. \left. \left. \left. \frac{\left(-\frac{27 \pi^2 w^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} + \frac{\sqrt{3} \sqrt{16 \pi^3 w^3 \gamma \theta + 243 \pi^4 w^6 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}}{\alpha} \right)^{1/3}}{6^{2/3} \pi} \right) \right) \right) \right\},$$

$$\frac{1}{2} \left(2 \mathbf{s} + 2 \sqrt{\left(w^2 - \frac{2^{2/3} w (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{3^{1/3} \alpha \left(-\frac{27 \pi^2 w^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} + \frac{\sqrt{3} \sqrt{16 \pi^3 w^3 \gamma \theta + 243 \pi^4 w^6 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}}{\alpha} \right)^{1/3}} \right)} \right. \right.$$

$$\left. \left. \left. \left. \frac{\left(-\frac{27 \pi^2 w^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} + \frac{\sqrt{3} \sqrt{16 \pi^3 w^3 \gamma \theta + 243 \pi^4 w^6 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}}{\alpha} \right)^{1/3}}{6^{2/3} \pi} \right) \right) \right) \right\},$$

$$\frac{1}{2} \left(2 \mathbf{s} - \sqrt{\left(4 \mathbf{s}^2 - 4 \left(\frac{\pi \mathbf{s}^2 - \pi w^2}{\pi} - \frac{(1 + i \sqrt{3}) w (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{6^{1/3} \alpha \left(-\frac{27 \pi^2 w^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} + \frac{\sqrt{3} \sqrt{16 \pi^3 w^3 \gamma \theta + 243 \pi^4 w^6 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}}{\alpha} \right)^{1/3}} \right)} \right)} \right. \right.$$

$$\left. \left. \left. \left. \frac{(1 - i \sqrt{3}) \left(-\frac{27 \pi^2 w^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} + \frac{\sqrt{3} \sqrt{16 \pi^3 w^3 \gamma \theta + 243 \pi^4 w^6 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}}{\alpha} \right)^{1/3}}{2 \times 6^{2/3} \pi} \right) \right) \right) \right\},$$

$$\frac{1}{2} \left(2s + \sqrt{\left(4s^2 - 4 \left(\frac{\pi s^2 - \pi w^2}{\pi} - \frac{(1 + i\sqrt{3}) w (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{6^{1/3} \alpha \left(-\frac{27 \pi^2 w^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} + \frac{\sqrt{3} \sqrt{16 \pi^3 w^3 \gamma \theta + 243 \pi^4 w^6 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}}{\alpha} \right)^{1/3} + \frac{(1 - i\sqrt{3}) \left(-\frac{27 \pi^2 w^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} + \frac{\sqrt{3} \sqrt{16 \pi^3 w^3 \gamma \theta + 243 \pi^4 w^6 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}}{\alpha} \right)^{1/3}}{2 \times 6^{2/3} \pi} \right) \right)},$$

$$\frac{1}{2} \left(2s - \sqrt{\left(4s^2 - 4 \left(\frac{\pi s^2 - \pi w^2}{\pi} - \frac{(1 - i\sqrt{3}) w (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{6^{1/3} \alpha \left(-\frac{27 \pi^2 w^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} + \frac{\sqrt{3} \sqrt{16 \pi^3 w^3 \gamma \theta + 243 \pi^4 w^6 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}}{\alpha} \right)^{1/3} + \frac{(1 + i\sqrt{3}) \left(-\frac{27 \pi^2 w^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} + \frac{\sqrt{3} \sqrt{16 \pi^3 w^3 \gamma \theta + 243 \pi^4 w^6 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}}{\alpha} \right)^{1/3}}{2 \times 6^{2/3} \pi} \right) \right)},$$

$$\frac{1}{2} \left(2s + \sqrt{\left(4s^2 - 4 \left(\frac{\pi s^2 - \pi w^2}{\pi} - \frac{(1 - i\sqrt{3}) w (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{6^{1/3} \alpha \left(-\frac{27 \pi^2 w^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} + \frac{\sqrt{3} \sqrt{16 \pi^3 w^3 \gamma \theta + 243 \pi^4 w^6 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}}{\alpha} \right)^{1/3} + \frac{(1 + i\sqrt{3}) \left(-\frac{27 \pi^2 w^3 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{1/3}}{\alpha} + \frac{\sqrt{3} \sqrt{16 \pi^3 w^3 \gamma \theta + 243 \pi^4 w^6 (\alpha \gamma \theta)^{2/3}}}{\alpha} \right)^{1/3}}{2 \times 6^{2/3} \pi} \right) \right)},$$

{s, 0, 5}, {w, 0, 5}], {\alpha, 0, 2\pi}, {\theta, 0, 2\pi}, {\gamma,

0,

2

\pi}]

Out[]:=

- ... **Power:** Infinite expression $\frac{1}{0}$ encountered.
- ... **Infinity:** Indeterminate expression $0 \pi^2 w^3$ ComplexInfinity encountered.
- ... **Power:** Infinite expression $\frac{1}{0}$ encountered.
- ... **Infinity:** Indeterminate expression $0 \sqrt{3}$ ComplexInfinity encountered.
- ... **Power:** Infinite expression $\frac{1}{0}$ encountered.
- ... **General:** Further output of Power::infy will be suppressed during this calculation.
- ... **Infinity:** Indeterminate expression $0 \pi^2 w^3$ ComplexInfinity encountered.
- ... **General:** Further output of Infinity::indet will be suppressed during this calculation.
- ... **Power:** Infinite expression $\frac{1}{0}$ encountered.
- ... **Infinity:** Indeterminate expression $0. 2^{2/3} w$ ComplexInfinity encountered.
- ... **Power:** Infinite expression $\frac{1}{0}$ encountered.
- ... **Infinity:** Indeterminate expression $0. 2^{2/3} w$ ComplexInfinity encountered.
- ... **Power:** Infinite expression $\frac{1}{0}$ encountered.
- ... **General:** Further output of Power::infy will be suppressed during this calculation.
- ... **Infinity:** Indeterminate expression $0. (1 + i \sqrt{3}) w$ ComplexInfinity encountered.
- ... **General:** Further output of Infinity::indet will be suppressed during this calculation.

- ... **Power:** Infinite expression $\frac{1}{0}$ encountered.
- ... **Infinity:** Indeterminate expression $0. 2^{2/3}$ w ComplexInfinity encountered.
- ... **Power:** Infinite expression $\frac{1}{0}$ encountered.
- ... **Infinity:** Indeterminate expression $0. 2^{2/3}$ w ComplexInfinity encountered.
- ... **Power:** Infinite expression $\frac{1}{0}$ encountered.
- ... **General:** Further output of Power::infy will be suppressed during this calculation.
- ... **Infinity:** Indeterminate expression $0. (1 + i \sqrt{3})$ w ComplexInfinity encountered.
- ... **General:** Further output of Infinity::indet will be suppressed during this calculation.

Naturally Equatable Formal Elements –

Using the Rote θ notation : $\sqrt{-(\infty - (\infty - 1))} = \sqrt{-1}$, or since,
 Con - Formal ∞ notation : $\text{Abs}[\infty - 1] := 1$, $\sqrt{(\infty - (\infty - 1))} = \sqrt{-1}$,
 - A balance from imaginary number infinity is found in l . How
 does this merge with the n th imaginary fabricated dimension,
 denoted "w*"? The w dimension solved with v - curvature method,
 denoted, "w" is also equatable with the solutions
 discovered therein as well as the root solution of an equated

$$\text{In}[*]:= \text{Solve}\left[v \sqrt{-1. \cdot l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2. \cdot r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2} == \sqrt{-c^2 l^2 \alpha^2 + c^2 x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 c^2 r x \gamma \theta + c^2 r^2 \theta^2 + c^2 l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}, l\right]$$

$$\text{Out}[*]:= \left\{ \left\{ l \rightarrow \frac{(0. + 1. i) \sqrt{1. c^2 x^2 \gamma^2 - 1. v^2 x^2 \gamma^2 - 2. c^2 r x \gamma \theta + 2. r v^2 x \gamma \theta + 1. c^2 r^2 \theta^2 - 1. r^2 v^2 \theta^2}}{\alpha \sqrt{-1. c^2 + 1. v^2 + 1. c^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1. v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}} \right\}, \left\{ l \rightarrow \frac{(0. + 1. i) \sqrt{1. c^2 x^2 \gamma^2 - 1. v^2 x^2 \gamma^2 - 2. c^2 r x \gamma \theta + 2. r v^2 x \gamma \theta + 1. c^2 r^2 \theta^2 - 1. r^2 v^2 \theta^2}}{\alpha \sqrt{-1. c^2 + 1. v^2 + 1. c^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1. v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}} \right\} \right\}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 l \alpha = w = & \left(\sqrt{(8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s +} \right. \\
 & \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - 1. \cdot q^2 v^2 + 2. \cdot q s v^2 - 1. \cdot s^2 v^2)} \right) / \\
 & \left(\sqrt{8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} - 1. \cdot v^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2} \right) = \\
 & \left((0. \cdot + 1. \cdot i) \right. \\
 & \left. \sqrt{1. \cdot c^2 x^2 \gamma^2 - 1. \cdot v^2 x^2 \gamma^2 - 2. \cdot c^2 r x \gamma \theta + 2. \cdot r v^2 x \gamma \theta + 1. \cdot c^2 r^2 \theta^2 - 1. \cdot r^2 v^2 \theta^2} \right) / \\
 & \left(\sqrt{-1. \cdot c^2 + 1. \cdot v^2 + 1. \cdot c^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1. \cdot v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{In[]:= Solve} & \left[\left((0. \cdot + 1. \cdot i) \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. \sqrt{1. \cdot c^2 x^2 \gamma^2 - 1. \cdot v^2 x^2 \gamma^2 - 2. \cdot c^2 r x \gamma \theta + 2. \cdot r v^2 x \gamma \theta + 1. \cdot c^2 r^2 \theta^2 - 1. \cdot r^2 v^2 \theta^2} \right) / \right. \\
 & \left. \left(\alpha \sqrt{-1. \cdot c^2 + 1. \cdot v^2 + 1. \cdot c^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1. \cdot v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2} \right) \right] \alpha = \\
 & \left(\sqrt{(8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s +} \right. \\
 & \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - 1. \cdot q^2 v^2 + 2. \cdot q s v^2 - 1. \cdot s^2 v^2)} \right) / \\
 & \left(\sqrt{8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} - 1. \cdot v^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2} \right), s]
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Out[]:=} & \left\{ \left\{ s \rightarrow \frac{1}{-8.98755 \times 10^{16} + v^2} \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 0.5 \left(-1. q \left(1.79751 \times 10^{17} - 2. v^2 \right) - 1. \sqrt{\left(3.23104 \times 10^{34} x^2 \gamma^2 - 7.19004 \times 10^{17} v^2 x^2 \gamma^2 + \right.} \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. \left. 4. v^4 x^2 \gamma^2 - 6.46209 \times 10^{34} r x \gamma \theta + 1.43801 \times 10^{18} r v^2 x \gamma \theta - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. \left. 8. r v^4 x \gamma \theta + 3.23104 \times 10^{34} r^2 \theta^2 - 7.19004 \times 10^{17} r^2 v^2 \theta^2 + 4. r^2 v^4 \theta^2 \right) \right) \right\}, \\
 & \left\{ s \rightarrow \frac{1}{-8.98755 \times 10^{16} + v^2} \right. \\
 & \left. 0.5 \left(-1. q \left(1.79751 \times 10^{17} - 2. v^2 \right) + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. \sqrt{\left(3.23104 \times 10^{34} x^2 \gamma^2 - 7.19004 \times 10^{17} v^2 x^2 \gamma^2 + 4. v^4 x^2 \gamma^2 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. \left. 6.46209 \times 10^{34} r x \gamma \theta + 1.43801 \times 10^{18} r v^2 x \gamma \theta - 8. r v^4 x \gamma \theta + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. \left. 3.23104 \times 10^{34} r^2 \theta^2 - 7.19004 \times 10^{17} r^2 v^2 \theta^2 + 4. r^2 v^4 \theta^2 \right) \right) \right\}
 \end{aligned}$$

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In[ ]:= Manipulate[ContourPlot3D[
  
$$\frac{1}{-8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} + v^2} \cdot 0.5 \cdot (-1 \cdot q (1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} - 2 \cdot v^2) + \sqrt{(3.231043485224996 \cdot 10^{34} x^2 \gamma^2 - 7.190041429894541 \cdot 10^{17} v^2 x^2 \gamma^2 + 4 \cdot v^4 x^2 \gamma^2 - 6.462086970449992 \cdot 10^{34} r x \gamma \theta + 1.4380082859789082 \cdot 10^{18} r v^2 x \gamma \theta - 8 \cdot r v^4 x \gamma \theta + 3.231043485224996 \cdot 10^{34} r^2 \theta^2 - 7.190041429894541 \cdot 10^{17} r^2 v^2 \theta^2 + 4 \cdot r^2 v^4 \theta^2)}),$$

  {x, 0, 5}, {r, 0, 5}, {\gamma, 0, 5}], {theta, 0, 2 \pi}, {v, 0, 2.99 \cdot 10^8}, {q,
  0,
  5}]

```

Out[]:=

$$\text{In[]:= Solve}\left[-\left(\left(1.\sqrt{\left(8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - 1. q^2 v^2 + 2. q s v^2 - 1. s^2 v^2\right)}\right) / \left(\sqrt{8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}\right)\right) \right. \\ \left. == -\sqrt{m^2 + 2 q^2 - 4 q s + 2 s^2} + 2 \sqrt{m^2 + q^2 - 2 q s + s^2} z + z^2, m\right]$$

$$\text{Out[]:= } \left\{ \left\{ m \rightarrow -0.5 \right. \right.$$

$$\sqrt{\left(-\left(8. \left(4.49378 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} q s + 4.49378 \times 10^{16} s^2 - 0.5 q^2 v^2 + 1. q s v^2 - 0.5 s^2 v^2 - 4.49378 \times 10^{16} z^2 + 0.5 v^2 z^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1. q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2. q s v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1. s^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.49378 \times 10^{16} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 0.5 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2\right)\right) / \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2\right) - 2. \sqrt{\left(\left(16. \left(4.49378 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} q s + 4.49378 \times 10^{16} s^2 - 0.5 q^2 v^2 + 1. q s v^2 - 0.5 s^2 v^2 - 4.49378 \times 10^{16} z^2 + 0.5 v^2 z^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1. q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2. q s v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1. s^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.49378 \times 10^{16} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 0.5 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2\right)\right)^2} / \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2\right)^2 - \left(16. \left(2.0194 \times 10^{33} q^4 - 8.07761 \times 10^{33} q^3 s + 1.21164 \times 10^{34} q^2 s^2 - 8.07761 \times 10^{33} q s^3 + 2.0194 \times 10^{33} s^4 - 4.49378 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^2 + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q^3 s v^2 - 2.69627 \times 10^{17} q^2 s^2 v^2 + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s^3 v^2 - 4.49378 \times 10^{16} s^4 v^2 + 0.25 q^4 v^4 - 1. q^3 s v^4 + 1.5 q^2 s^2 v^4 - 1. q s^3 v^4 + 0.25 s^4 v^4 - 4.0388 \times 10^{33} q^2 z^2 + 8.07761 \times 10^{33} q s z^2 - 4.0388 \times 10^{33} s^2 z^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s v^2 z^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 v^2 z^2 - 0.5 q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1. q s v^4 z^2 - 0.5 s^2 v^4 z^2 + 2.0194 \times 10^{33} z^4 - 4.49378 \times 10^{16} v^2\right.\right.$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& z^4 + 0.25 v^4 z^4 - 8.07761 \times 10^{33} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.23104 \times 10^{34} q^3 s \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.84657 \times 10^{34} q^2 s^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.23104 \times 10^{34} q s^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.07761 \times 10^{33} \\
& s^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.19004 \times 10^{17} q^3 s v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.07851 \times 10^{18} q^2 s^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.19004 \times 10^{17} q s^3 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.79751 \times 10^{17} s^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1. q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4. q^3 s v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 6. q^2 s^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4. q s^3 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1. s^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.0388 \times 10^{33} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.07761 \times 10^{33} q s z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.0388 \times 10^{33} s^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 0.5 q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1. q s v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 0.5 s^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.0388 \times 10^{33} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 0.5 v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.07761 \times 10^{33} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 3.23104 \times 10^{34} q^3 s \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.84657 \times 10^{34} \\
& q^2 s^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 3.23104 \times 10^{34} q s^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.07761 \times 10^{33} s^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 7.19004 \times 10^{17} q^3 s v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.07851 \times 10^{18} q^2 s^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 7.19004 \times 10^{17} q s^3 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.79751 \times 10^{17} s^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1. q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4. q^3 s v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6. q^2 s^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4. q s^3 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1. s^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.0194 \times 10^{33} \\
& z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.49378 \times 10^{16} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 0.25 v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) / \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^2) \Big\}, \\
\{m \rightarrow 0.5 \sqrt{(-((8. (4.49378 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} q s + 4.49378 \times 10^{16} s^2 - \\
& 0.5 q^2 v^2 + 1. q s v^2 - 0.5 s^2 v^2 - 4.49378 \times 10^{16} z^2 + 0.5 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1. q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2. q s v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1. s^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.49378 \times 10^{16} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 0.5 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)) / \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)) - \\
& 2. \sqrt{((16. (4.49378 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} q s + 4.49378 \times 10^{16} s^2 - \\
& 0.5 q^2 v^2 + 1. q s v^2 - 0.5 s^2 v^2 - 4.49378 \times 10^{16} z^2 + 0.5 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1. q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2. q s v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1. s^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.49378 \times 10^{16} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 0.5 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^2) / \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^2 - \\
& (16. (2.0194 \times 10^{33} q^4 - 8.07761 \times 10^{33} q^3 s + 1.21164 \times 10^{34} q^2 s^2 - \\
& 8.07761 \times 10^{33} q s^3 + 2.0194 \times 10^{33} s^4 - 4.49378 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^2 + \\
& 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q^3 s v^2 - 2.69627 \times 10^{17} q^2 s^2 v^2 + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s^3 v^2 - \\
& 4.49378 \times 10^{16} s^4 v^2 + 0.25 q^4 v^4 - 1. q^3 s v^4 + 1.5 q^2 s^2 v^4 - 1. q s^3 v^4 + \\
& 0.25 s^4 v^4 - 4.0388 \times 10^{33} q^2 z^2 + 8.07761 \times 10^{33} q s z^2 - 4.0388 \times 10^{33} s^2 z^2 + \\
& 8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s v^2 z^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 0.5 q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1. q s v^4 z^2 - 0.5 s^2 v^4 z^2 + 2.0194 \times 10^{33} z^4 - 4.49378 \times 10^{16} v^2 \\
& z^4 + 0.25 v^4 z^4 - 8.07761 \times 10^{33} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.23104 \times 10^{34} q^3 s \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.84657 \times 10^{34} q^2 s^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.23104 \times 10^{34} q s^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.07761 \times 10^{33} \\
& s^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.19004 \times 10^{17} q^3 s v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.07851 \times 10^{18} q^2 s^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.19004 \times 10^{17} q s^3 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.79751 \times 10^{17} s^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1. q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4. q^3 s v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 6. q^2 s^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4. q s^3 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1. s^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.0388 \times 10^{33} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.07761 \times 10^{33} q s z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.0388 \times 10^{33} s^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 0.5 q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1. q s v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 0.5 s^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 4.0388 \times 10^{33} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 0.5 v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.07761 \times 10^{33} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 3.23104 \times 10^{34} q^3 s \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.84657 \times 10^{34} \\
 & q^2 s^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 3.23104 \times 10^{34} q s^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.07761 \times 10^{33} s^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 7.19004 \times 10^{17} q^3 s v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.07851 \times 10^{18} q^2 s^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 7.19004 \times 10^{17} q s^3 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.79751 \times 10^{17} s^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1. q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4. q^3 s v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 6. q^2 s^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4. q s^3 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1. s^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.0194 \times 10^{33} \\
 & z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.49378 \times 10^{16} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 0.25 v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) / \\
 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^2) \Big\}, \\
 & \left\{ m \rightarrow -0.5 \sqrt{\left(- \left(8. (4.49378 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} q s + 4.49378 \times 10^{16} s^2 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad 0.5 q^2 v^2 + 1. q s v^2 - 0.5 s^2 v^2 - 4.49378 \times 10^{16} z^2 + 0.5 v^2 z^2 - \\
 & \quad 8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1. q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2. q s v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 1. s^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.49378 \times 10^{16} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 0.5 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right) \right) \right) / \\
 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2) + \\
 & 2. \sqrt{\left(\left(16. (4.49378 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} q s + 4.49378 \times 10^{16} s^2 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad 0.5 q^2 v^2 + 1. q s v^2 - 0.5 s^2 v^2 - 4.49378 \times 10^{16} z^2 + 0.5 v^2 z^2 - \\
 & \quad 8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1. q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2. q s v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 1. s^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.49378 \times 10^{16} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 0.5 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right) \right) \right) / \\
 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^2 - \\
 & (16. (2.0194 \times 10^{33} q^4 - 8.07761 \times 10^{33} q^3 s + 1.21164 \times 10^{34} q^2 s^2 - \\
 & \quad 8.07761 \times 10^{33} q s^3 + 2.0194 \times 10^{33} s^4 - 4.49378 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^2 + \\
 & \quad 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q^3 s v^2 - 2.69627 \times 10^{17} q^2 s^2 v^2 + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s^3 v^2 - \\
 & \quad 4.49378 \times 10^{16} s^4 v^2 + 0.25 q^4 v^4 - 1. q^3 s v^4 + 1.5 q^2 s^2 v^4 - 1. q s^3 v^4 + \\
 & \quad 0.25 s^4 v^4 - 4.0388 \times 10^{33} q^2 z^2 + 8.07761 \times 10^{33} q s z^2 - 4.0388 \times 10^{33} s^2 z^2 + \\
 & \quad 8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s v^2 z^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
 & \quad 0.5 q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1. q s v^4 z^2 - 0.5 s^2 v^4 z^2 + 2.0194 \times 10^{33} z^4 - 4.49378 \times 10^{16} v^2 \\
 & \quad z^4 + 0.25 v^4 z^4 - 8.07761 \times 10^{33} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.23104 \times 10^{34} q^3 s \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 4.84657 \times 10^{34} q^2 s^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.23104 \times 10^{34} q s^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.07761 \times 10^{33} \\
 & \quad s^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.19004 \times 10^{17} q^3 s v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 1.07851 \times 10^{18} q^2 s^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.19004 \times 10^{17} q s^3 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 1.79751 \times 10^{17} s^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1. q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4. q^3 s v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 6. q^2 s^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4. q s^3 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1. s^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 4.0388 \times 10^{33} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.07761 \times 10^{33} q s z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.0388 \times 10^{33} s^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 0.5 q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1. q s v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 0.5 s^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 4.0388 \times 10^{33} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 0.5 v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.07761 \times 10^{33} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 3.23104 \times 10^{34} q^3 s \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.84657 \times 10^{34} \\
 & \quad q^2 s^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 3.23104 \times 10^{34} q s^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.07761 \times 10^{33} s^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 7.19004 \times 10^{17} q^3 s v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.07851 \times 10^{18} q^2 s^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 7.19004 \times 10^{17} q s^3 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.79751 \times 10^{17} s^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1. q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4. q^3 s v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 6. q^2 s^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4. q s^3 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1. s^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.0194 \times 10^{33} \\
 & \quad z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.49378 \times 10^{16} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 0.25 v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) / \\
 & \left. \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right) \right) \Bigg\}, \\
 & \left\{ m \rightarrow 0.5 \sqrt{\left(- \left(8. \left(4.49378 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} q s + 4.49378 \times 10^{16} s^2 - \right. \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad 0.5 q^2 v^2 + 1. q s v^2 - 0.5 s^2 v^2 - 4.49378 \times 10^{16} z^2 + 0.5 v^2 z^2 - \\
 & \quad 8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1. q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2. q s v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 1. s^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.49378 \times 10^{16} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 0.5 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right) \right) \right) / \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right) \right) + \\
 & 2. \sqrt{\left(\left(16. \left(4.49378 \times 10^{16} q^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} q s + 4.49378 \times 10^{16} s^2 - \right. \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad 0.5 q^2 v^2 + 1. q s v^2 - 0.5 s^2 v^2 - 4.49378 \times 10^{16} z^2 + 0.5 v^2 z^2 - \\
 & \quad 8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1. q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2. q s v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 1. s^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.49378 \times 10^{16} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 0.5 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right) \right) \right) / \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right) \right) - \\
 & \left. \left(16. \left(2.0194 \times 10^{33} q^4 - 8.07761 \times 10^{33} q^3 s + 1.21164 \times 10^{34} q^2 s^2 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad 8.07761 \times 10^{33} q s^3 + 2.0194 \times 10^{33} s^4 - 4.49378 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^2 + \\
 & \quad 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q^3 s v^2 - 2.69627 \times 10^{17} q^2 s^2 v^2 + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s^3 v^2 - \\
 & \quad 4.49378 \times 10^{16} s^4 v^2 + 0.25 q^4 v^4 - 1. q^3 s v^4 + 1.5 q^2 s^2 v^4 - 1. q s^3 v^4 + \\
 & \quad 0.25 s^4 v^4 - 4.0388 \times 10^{33} q^2 z^2 + 8.07761 \times 10^{33} q s z^2 - 4.0388 \times 10^{33} s^2 z^2 + \\
 & \quad 8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s v^2 z^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
 & \quad 0.5 q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1. q s v^4 z^2 - 0.5 s^2 v^4 z^2 + 2.0194 \times 10^{33} z^4 - \\
 & \quad 4.49378 \times 10^{16} v^2 z^4 + 0.25 v^4 z^4 - 8.07761 \times 10^{33} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 3.23104 \times 10^{34} q^3 s \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.84657 \times 10^{34} q^2 s^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 3.23104 \times 10^{34} q s^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.07761 \times 10^{33} s^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.19004 \times 10^{17} q^3 s v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 1.07851 \times 10^{18} q^2 s^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.19004 \times 10^{17} q s^3 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 1.79751 \times 10^{17} s^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1. q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4. q^3 s v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 6. q^2 s^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4. q s^3 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1. s^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 4.0388 \times 10^{33} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.07761 \times 10^{33} q s z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 4.0388 \times 10^{33} s^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q s v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} s^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 0.5 q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1. q s v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 0.5 s^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 4.0388 \times 10^{33} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 0.5 v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.07761 \times 10^{33} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 3.23104 \times 10^{34} q^3 s \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.84657 \times 10^{34} \\
 & q^2 s^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 3.23104 \times 10^{34} q s^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.07761 \times 10^{33} s^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.79751 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 7.19004 \times 10^{17} q^3 s v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.07851 \times 10^{18} q^2 s^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 7.19004 \times 10^{17} q s^3 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.79751 \times 10^{17} s^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1. q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4. q^3 s v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 6. q^2 s^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4. q s^3 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1. s^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.0194 \times 10^{33} \\
 & z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.49378 \times 10^{16} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 0.25 v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) / \\
 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^2) \} \}
 \end{aligned}$$

In[]:= Manipulate[

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{ContourPlot3D} \left[0.5 \sqrt{\left(- \left(\left(8. \left(4.493775893684088 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q s + \right. \right. \right. \right. \right. \\
 & 4.493775893684088 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - 0.5 \cdot q^2 v^2 + 1. \cdot q s v^2 - 0.5 \cdot s^2 v^2 - \\
 & 4.493775893684088 \cdot 10^{16} z^2 + 0.5 \cdot v^2 z^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} \\
 & s^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1. \cdot q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2. \cdot q s v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1. \cdot s^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.493775893684088 \cdot 10^{16} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 0.5 \cdot v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2) \left. \right) /} \\
 & (8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} - 1. \cdot v^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2) \left. \right) + \\
 & 2. \cdot \sqrt{\left(\left(16. \left(4.493775893684088 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q s + \right. \right. \right. \right. \\
 & 4.493775893684088 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 - 0.5 \cdot q^2 v^2 + 1. \cdot q s v^2 - 0.5 \cdot s^2 v^2 - \\
 & 4.493775893684088 \cdot 10^{16} z^2 + 0.5 \cdot v^2 z^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} \\
 & q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1. \cdot q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2. \cdot q s v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1. \cdot s^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.493775893684088 \cdot 10^{16} \\
 & z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 0.5 \cdot v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2) \left. \right) /} (8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} - \\
 & 1. \cdot v^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^2 - \\
 & (16. \cdot (2.0194021782656225 \cdot 10^{33} q^4 - 8.07760871306249 \cdot 10^{33} q^3 \\
 & s + 1.2116413069593733 \cdot 10^{34} q^2 s^2 - 8.07760871306249 \cdot 10^{33} q \\
 & s^3 + 2.0194021782656225 \cdot 10^{33} s^4 - 4.493775893684088 \cdot 10^{16} q^4 \\
 & v^2 + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q^3 s v^2 - 2.6962655362104528 \cdot 10^{17} q^2 \\
 & s^2 v^2 + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s^3 v^2 - 4.493775893684088 \cdot 10^{16} \\
 & s^4 v^2 + 0.25 \cdot q^4 v^4 - 1. \cdot q^3 s v^4 + 1.5 \cdot q^2 s^2 v^4 - 1. \cdot q s^3 v^4 + 0.25 \cdot s^4 \\
 & v^4 - 4.038804356531245 \cdot 10^{33} q^2 z^2 + 8.07760871306249 \cdot 10^{33} q s \\
 & z^2 - 4.038804356531245 \cdot 10^{33} s^2 z^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 v^2 \\
 & z^2 - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s v^2 z^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 v^2 \\
 & z^2 - 0.5 \cdot q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1. \cdot q s v^4 z^2 - 0.5 \cdot s^2 v^4 z^2 + 2.0194021782656225 \cdot 10^{33} \\
 & z^4 - 4.493775893684088 \cdot 10^{16} v^2 z^4 + 0.25 \cdot v^4 z^4 - 8.07760871306249 \cdot 10^{33} \\
 & q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.231043485224996 \cdot 10^{34} q^3 s \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 4.846565227837493 \cdot 10^{34} q^2 s^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.231043485224996 \cdot 10^{34} q s^3 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.07760871306249 \cdot 10^{33} s^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} \\
 & q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.190041429894541 \cdot 10^{17} q^3 s v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.0785062144841811 \cdot 10^{18} q^2 s^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.190041429894541 \cdot 10^{17} \\
 & q s^3 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} s^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1. \cdot q^4 \\
 & v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4. \cdot q^3 s v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6. \cdot q^2 s^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4. \cdot q s^3 v^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 - 1. \cdot s^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.038804356531245 \cdot 10^{33} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 8.07760871306249 \cdot 10^{33} q s z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.038804356531245 \cdot 10^{33} \\
 & s^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} q s v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} s^2 \\
 & v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 0.5 \cdot q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1. \cdot q s v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 0.5 \cdot s^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.038804356531245 \cdot 10^{33} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} \\
 & v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 0.5 \cdot v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.07760871306249 \cdot 10^{33} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 3.231043485224996 \cdot 10^{34} q^3 s \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.846565227837493 \cdot 10^{34} \\
 & q^2 s^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 3.231043485224996 \cdot 10^{34} q s^3 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 8.07760871306249 \cdot 10^{33} s^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} \\
 & q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 7.190041429894541 \cdot 10^{17} q^3 s v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.0785062144841811 \cdot 10^{18} q^2 s^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 7.190041429894541 \cdot 10^{17} \\
 & q s^3 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} s^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1. \cdot q^4 \\
 & v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4. \cdot q^3 s v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 6. \cdot q^2 s^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4. \cdot q s^3 v^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 + 1. \cdot s^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.0194021782656225 \cdot 10^{33} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 4.493775893684088 \cdot 10^{16} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 0.25 \cdot v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4) / \\
 & (8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} - 1. \cdot v^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^2),
 \end{aligned}$$

$\{q, 0, 5\}, \{s, 0, 5\}, \{z, 0, 5\}], \{\beta, 0, \pi / 2\},$
 $\{v,$
 $0,$
 $c\}]$

Out[]=

Power: Infinite expression $\frac{1}{0}$ encountered.

Power: Infinite expression $\frac{1}{0}$ encountered.

Power: Infinite expression $\frac{1}{0}$ encountered.

General: Further output of Power::infy will be suppressed during this calculation.

Infinity: Indeterminate expression ComplexInfinity + ComplexInfinity encountered.

Infinity: Indeterminate expression ComplexInfinity + ComplexInfinity encountered.

Infinity: Indeterminate expression 0. ComplexInfinity encountered.

General: Further output of Infinity::indet will be suppressed during this calculation.

In[]:= c := 2.99792458` * 10^8

In[]:= Solve[m == 0.5`  $\sqrt{-((8.` (4.493775893684088` * ^16 q^2 - 8.987551787368176` * ^16 q s + 4.493775893684088` * ^16 s^2 - 0.5` q^2 v^2 + 1.` q s v^2 - 0.5` s^2 v^2 - 4.493775893684088` * ^16 z^2 + 0.5` v^2 z^2 - 8.987551787368176` * ^16 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.7975103574736352` * ^17 q s \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.987551787368176` * ^16 s^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.` q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.` q s v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.` s^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 +$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (4.493775893684088 \cdot z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 0.5 \cdot v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2) / \\
 & (8.987551787368176 \cdot \sin[\beta]^2 - 1 \cdot v^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad v^2 \sin[\beta]^2) + \\
 2 \cdot & \sqrt{\left((16 \cdot (4.493775893684088 \cdot q^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot q s + \right. \\
 & \quad 4.493775893684088 \cdot s^2 - 0.5 \cdot q^2 v^2 + 1 \cdot q s v^2 - \\
 & \quad 0.5 \cdot s^2 v^2 - 4.493775893684088 \cdot z^2 + 0.5 \cdot v^2 z^2 - \\
 & \quad 8.987551787368176 \cdot q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot q s \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot s^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 1 \cdot q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2 \cdot q s v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1 \cdot s^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad \left. 4.493775893684088 \cdot z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 0.5 \cdot v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2) \right)^2 / \\
 & (8.987551787368176 \cdot \sin[\beta]^2 - 1 \cdot v^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^2 - \\
 (16 \cdot & (2.0194021782656225 \cdot q^4 - 8.07760871306249 \cdot q^3 \\
 & \quad s + 1.2116413069593733 \cdot q^2 s^2 - 8.07760871306249 \cdot q^3 q \\
 & \quad s^3 + 2.0194021782656225 \cdot q^4 s^4 - 4.493775893684088 \cdot q^4 \\
 & \quad v^2 + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot q^3 s v^2 - 2.6962655362104528 \cdot q^2 s^2 v^2 + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot q s^3 v^2 - 4.493775893684088 \cdot s^4 \\
 & \quad s^4 v^2 + 0.25 \cdot q^4 v^4 - 1 \cdot q^3 s v^4 + 1.5 \cdot q^2 s^2 v^4 - 1 \cdot q s^3 v^4 + 0.25 \cdot s^4 \\
 & \quad v^4 - 4.038804356531245 \cdot q^2 z^2 + 8.07760871306249 \cdot q s \\
 & \quad z^2 - 4.038804356531245 \cdot s^2 z^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot q^2 v^2 \\
 & \quad z^2 - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot q s v^2 z^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot s^2 v^2 \\
 & \quad z^2 - 0.5 \cdot q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1 \cdot q s v^4 z^2 - 0.5 \cdot s^2 v^4 z^2 + 2.0194021782656225 \cdot q^3 \\
 & \quad z^4 - 4.493775893684088 \cdot q^2 v^2 z^4 + 0.25 \cdot v^4 z^4 - 8.07760871306249 \cdot q^3 \\
 & \quad q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.231043485224996 \cdot q^3 s \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 4.846565227837493 \cdot q^2 s^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.231043485224996 \cdot q s^3 \\
 & \quad \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.07760871306249 \cdot q^3 s^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot q^4 \\
 & \quad q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.190041429894541 \cdot q^3 s v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 1.0785062144841811 \cdot q^2 s^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.190041429894541 \cdot q^3 \\
 & \quad q s^3 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot q^4 s^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1 \cdot q^4 \\
 & \quad v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4 \cdot q^3 s v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6 \cdot q^2 s^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4 \cdot q s^3 v^4 \\
 & \quad \sin[\beta]^2 - 1 \cdot s^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.038804356531245 \cdot q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 8.07760871306249 \cdot q s z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.038804356531245 \cdot s^3 \\
 & \quad s^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 1.7975103574736352 \cdot q s v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot s^2 \\
 & \quad v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 0.5 \cdot q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1 \cdot q s v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 0.5 \cdot s^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \quad \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.038804356531245 \cdot q^3 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot q^2 \\
 & \quad v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 0.5 \cdot v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.07760871306249 \cdot q^3 \\
 & \quad q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 3.231043485224996 \cdot q^3 s \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.846565227837493 \cdot q^3 \\
 & \quad q^2 s^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 3.231043485224996 \cdot q s^3 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 8.07760871306249 \cdot q^3 s^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot q^4 \\
 & \quad q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 7.190041429894541 \cdot q^3 s v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 1.0785062144841811 \cdot q^2 s^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 7.190041429894541 \cdot q^3 \\
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\left(\frac{q s^3 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot s^{17} v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1 \cdot q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4 \cdot q^3 s v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 6 \cdot q^2 s^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4 \cdot q s^3 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1 \cdot s^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.0194021782656225 \cdot s^{33} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.493775893684088 \cdot s^{16} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 0.25 \cdot v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)}{(8.987551787368176 \cdot s^{16} - 1 \cdot v^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot s^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^2} \right), v]$$

Out[+]= { {v → Root[

$$\begin{aligned} & 2.72907296190758 \times 10^{92} m^4 + 1.99435302303285 \times 10^{79} z^2 - 5.45814592381516 \times 10^{92} m^2 z^2 + \\ & 2.72907296190758 \times 10^{92} z^4 + 2.04221749558564 \times 10^{82} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\ & 5.45814592381516 \times 10^{92} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.99435302303285 \times 10^{79} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\ & 1.09162918476303 \times 10^{93} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.45814592381516 \times 10^{92} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\ & 4.08443499117128 \times 10^{82} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.72907296190758 \times 10^{92} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\ & 5.45814592381516 \times 10^{92} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.72907296190758 \times 10^{92} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\ & (1.41707305305719 \times 10^{65} - 1.21460127361635 \times 10^{76} m^4 - \\ & 4.43803400573641 \times 10^{62} z^2 + 2.42920254723271 \times 10^{76} m^2 z^2 - \\ & 1.21460127361635 \times 10^{76} z^4 - 1.02128390341028 \times 10^{66} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\ & 2.42920254723271 \times 10^{76} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.43803400573641 \times 10^{62} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\ & 4.85840509446541 \times 10^{76} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.42920254723271 \times 10^{76} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\ & 1.47573858559769 \times 10^{66} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.21460127361635 \times 10^{76} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\ & 2.42920254723271 \times 10^{76} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.21460127361635 \times 10^{76} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \#1^2 + \\ & (-4.13670478075728 \times 10^{48} + 2.02713926275805 \times 10^{59} m^4 + \\ & 2.46898939262524 \times 10^{45} z^2 - 4.05427852551609 \times 10^{59} m^2 z^2 + \\ & 2.02713926275805 \times 10^{59} z^4 + 1.90750642610774 \times 10^{49} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\ & 4.05427852551609 \times 10^{59} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.46898939262524 \times 10^{45} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\ & 8.1085570510322 \times 10^{59} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.05427852551609 \times 10^{59} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\ & 2.16033093991256 \times 10^{49} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.02713926275805 \times 10^{59} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\ & 4.05427852551609 \times 10^{59} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.02713926275805 \times 10^{59} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \#1^4 + \\ & (3.94244217957789 \times 10^{31} - 1.50366440955749 \times 10^{42} m^4 + \\ & 3.00732881911498 \times 10^{42} m^2 z^2 - 1.50366440955749 \times 10^{42} z^4 - \\ & 1.57697687183116 \times 10^{32} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.00732881911498 \times 10^{42} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\ & 6.01465763822995 \times 10^{42} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.00732881911498 \times 10^{42} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\ & 1.57697687183116 \times 10^{32} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.50366440955749 \times 10^{42} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\ & 3.00732881911498 \times 10^{42} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.50366440955749 \times 10^{42} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \#1^6 + \\ & (-1.21730575452964 \times 10^{14} + 4.18263072394993 \times 10^{24} m^4 - 8.3652614478999 \times 10^{24} \\ & m^2 z^2 + 4.18263072394993 \times 10^{24} z^4 + 4.86922301811856 \times 10^{14} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\ & 8.3652614478999 \times 10^{24} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.67305228957997 \times 10^{25} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\ & 8.3652614478999 \times 10^{24} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.86922301811856 \times 10^{14} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\ & 4.18263072394993 \times 10^{24} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.3652614478999 \times 10^{24} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\ & 4.18263072394993 \times 10^{24} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \#1^8 \& , 1] \}, \end{aligned}$$

$$\{v \rightarrow \text{Root}[2.72907296190758 \times 10^{92} m^4 + 1.99435302303285 \times 10^{79} z^2 - 5.45814592381516 \times 10^{92} m^2 z^2 + 2.72907296190758 \times 10^{92} z^4 +$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.04221749558564 \times 10^{82} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.45814592381516 \times 10^{92} \text{m}^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.99435302303285 \times 10^{79} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.09162918476303 \times 10^{93} \text{m}^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.45814592381516 \times 10^{92} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 4.08443499117128 \times 10^{82} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.72907296190758 \times 10^{92} \text{m}^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 5.45814592381516 \times 10^{92} \text{m}^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.72907296190758 \times 10^{92} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & (1.41707305305719 \times 10^{65} - 1.21460127361635 \times 10^{76} \text{m}^4 - \\
 & \quad 4.43803400573641 \times 10^{62} z^2 + 2.42920254723271 \times 10^{76} \text{m}^2 z^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.21460127361635 \times 10^{76} z^4 - 1.02128390341028 \times 10^{66} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 2.42920254723271 \times 10^{76} \text{m}^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.43803400573641 \times 10^{62} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 4.85840509446541 \times 10^{76} \text{m}^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.42920254723271 \times 10^{76} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 1.47573858559769 \times 10^{66} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.21460127361635 \times 10^{76} \text{m}^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 2.42920254723271 \times 10^{76} \text{m}^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.21460127361635 \times 10^{76} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \#1^2 + \\
 & (-4.13670478075728 \times 10^{48} + 2.02713926275805 \times 10^{59} \text{m}^4 + \\
 & \quad 2.46898939262524 \times 10^{45} z^2 - 4.05427852551609 \times 10^{59} \text{m}^2 z^2 + \\
 & \quad 2.02713926275805 \times 10^{59} z^4 + 1.90750642610774 \times 10^{49} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 4.05427852551609 \times 10^{59} \text{m}^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.46898939262524 \times 10^{45} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 8.1085570510322 \times 10^{59} \text{m}^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.05427852551609 \times 10^{59} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 2.16033093991256 \times 10^{49} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.02713926275805 \times 10^{59} \text{m}^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 4.05427852551609 \times 10^{59} \text{m}^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.02713926275805 \times 10^{59} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \#1^4 + \\
 & (3.94244217957789 \times 10^{31} - 1.50366440955749 \times 10^{42} \text{m}^4 + \\
 & \quad 3.00732881911498 \times 10^{42} \text{m}^2 z^2 - 1.50366440955749 \times 10^{42} z^4 - \\
 & \quad 1.57697687183116 \times 10^{32} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.00732881911498 \times 10^{42} \text{m}^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 6.01465763822995 \times 10^{42} \text{m}^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.00732881911498 \times 10^{42} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 1.57697687183116 \times 10^{32} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.50366440955749 \times 10^{42} \text{m}^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 3.00732881911498 \times 10^{42} \text{m}^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.50366440955749 \times 10^{42} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \#1^6 + \\
 & (-1.21730575452964 \times 10^{14} + 4.18263072394993 \times 10^{24} \text{m}^4 - 8.3652614478999 \times 10^{24} \\
 & \quad \text{m}^2 z^2 + 4.18263072394993 \times 10^{24} z^4 + 4.86922301811856 \times 10^{14} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 8.3652614478999 \times 10^{24} \text{m}^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.67305228957997 \times 10^{25} \text{m}^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 8.3652614478999 \times 10^{24} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.86922301811856 \times 10^{14} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 4.18263072394993 \times 10^{24} \text{m}^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.3652614478999 \times 10^{24} \text{m}^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 4.18263072394993 \times 10^{24} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \#1^8 \&, 2\}, \\
 & \{v \rightarrow \text{Root}[2.72907296190758 \times 10^{92} \text{m}^4 + 1.99435302303285 \times 10^{79} z^2 - \\
 & \quad 5.45814592381516 \times 10^{92} \text{m}^2 z^2 + 2.72907296190758 \times 10^{92} z^4 + \\
 & \quad 2.04221749558564 \times 10^{82} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.45814592381516 \times 10^{92} \text{m}^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.99435302303285 \times 10^{79} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 1.09162918476303 \times 10^{93} \text{m}^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 5.45814592381516 \times 10^{92} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 4.08443499117128 \times 10^{82} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.72907296190758 \times 10^{92} \text{m}^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 5.45814592381516 \times 10^{92} \text{m}^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 2.72907296190758 \times 10^{92} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad (1.41707305305719 \times 10^{65} - 1.21460127361635 \times 10^{76} \text{m}^4 - \\
 & \quad \quad 4.43803400573641 \times 10^{62} z^2 + 2.42920254723271 \times 10^{76} \text{m}^2 z^2 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.21460127361635 \times 10^{76} z^4 - 1.02128390341028 \times 10^{66} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.42920254723271 \times 10^{76} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.43803400573641 \times 10^{62} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 4.85840509446541 \times 10^{76} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.42920254723271 \times 10^{76} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.47573858559769 \times 10^{66} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.21460127361635 \times 10^{76} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.42920254723271 \times 10^{76} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.21460127361635 \times 10^{76} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \#1^2 + \\
 & (-4.13670478075728 \times 10^{48} + 2.02713926275805 \times 10^{59} m^4 + \\
 & 2.46898939262524 \times 10^{45} z^2 - 4.05427852551609 \times 10^{59} m^2 z^2 + \\
 & 2.02713926275805 \times 10^{59} z^4 + 1.90750642610774 \times 10^{49} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 4.05427852551609 \times 10^{59} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.46898939262524 \times 10^{45} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.1085570510322 \times 10^{59} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.05427852551609 \times 10^{59} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.16033093991256 \times 10^{49} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.02713926275805 \times 10^{59} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 4.05427852551609 \times 10^{59} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.02713926275805 \times 10^{59} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \#1^4 + \\
 & (3.94244217957789 \times 10^{31} - 1.50366440955749 \times 10^{42} m^4 + \\
 & 3.00732881911498 \times 10^{42} m^2 z^2 - 1.50366440955749 \times 10^{42} z^4 - \\
 & 1.57697687183116 \times 10^{32} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.00732881911498 \times 10^{42} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 6.01465763822995 \times 10^{42} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.00732881911498 \times 10^{42} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.57697687183116 \times 10^{32} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.50366440955749 \times 10^{42} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.00732881911498 \times 10^{42} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.50366440955749 \times 10^{42} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \#1^6 + \\
 & (-1.21730575452964 \times 10^{14} + 4.18263072394993 \times 10^{24} m^4 - 8.3652614478999 \times 10^{24} \\
 & m^2 z^2 + 4.18263072394993 \times 10^{24} z^4 + 4.86922301811856 \times 10^{14} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 8.3652614478999 \times 10^{24} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.67305228957997 \times 10^{25} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 8.3652614478999 \times 10^{24} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.86922301811856 \times 10^{14} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 4.18263072394993 \times 10^{24} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.3652614478999 \times 10^{24} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 4.18263072394993 \times 10^{24} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \#1^8 \& , 3 \} , \\
 & \{v \rightarrow \text{Root}[2.72907296190758 \times 10^{92} m^4 + 1.99435302303285 \times 10^{79} z^2 - \\
 & 5.45814592381516 \times 10^{92} m^2 z^2 + 2.72907296190758 \times 10^{92} z^4 + \\
 & 2.04221749558564 \times 10^{82} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.45814592381516 \times 10^{92} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.99435302303285 \times 10^{79} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.09162918476303 \times 10^{93} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.45814592381516 \times 10^{92} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 4.08443499117128 \times 10^{82} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.72907296190758 \times 10^{92} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 5.45814592381516 \times 10^{92} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.72907296190758 \times 10^{92} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & (1.41707305305719 \times 10^{65} - 1.21460127361635 \times 10^{76} m^4 - \\
 & 4.43803400573641 \times 10^{62} z^2 + 2.42920254723271 \times 10^{76} m^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.21460127361635 \times 10^{76} z^4 - 1.02128390341028 \times 10^{66} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.42920254723271 \times 10^{76} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.43803400573641 \times 10^{62} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 4.85840509446541 \times 10^{76} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.42920254723271 \times 10^{76} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.47573858559769 \times 10^{66} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.21460127361635 \times 10^{76} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.42920254723271 \times 10^{76} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.21460127361635 \times 10^{76} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \#1^2 + \\
 & (-4.13670478075728 \times 10^{48} + 2.02713926275805 \times 10^{59} m^4 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.46898939262524 \times 10^{45} z^2 - 4.05427852551609 \times 10^{59} m^2 z^2 + \\
& 2.02713926275805 \times 10^{59} z^4 + 1.90750642610774 \times 10^{49} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.05427852551609 \times 10^{59} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.46898939262524 \times 10^{45} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.1085570510322 \times 10^{59} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.05427852551609 \times 10^{59} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.16033093991256 \times 10^{49} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.02713926275805 \times 10^{59} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.05427852551609 \times 10^{59} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.02713926275805 \times 10^{59} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \#1^4 + \\
& (3.94244217957789 \times 10^{31} - 1.50366440955749 \times 10^{42} m^4 + \\
& 3.00732881911498 \times 10^{42} m^2 z^2 - 1.50366440955749 \times 10^{42} z^4 - \\
& 1.57697687183116 \times 10^{32} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.00732881911498 \times 10^{42} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 6.01465763822995 \times 10^{42} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.00732881911498 \times 10^{42} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.57697687183116 \times 10^{32} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.50366440955749 \times 10^{42} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.00732881911498 \times 10^{42} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.50366440955749 \times 10^{42} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \#1^6 + \\
& (-1.21730575452964 \times 10^{14} + 4.18263072394993 \times 10^{24} m^4 - 8.3652614478999 \times 10^{24} \\
& m^2 z^2 + 4.18263072394993 \times 10^{24} z^4 + 4.86922301811856 \times 10^{14} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.3652614478999 \times 10^{24} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.67305228957997 \times 10^{25} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.3652614478999 \times 10^{24} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.86922301811856 \times 10^{14} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 4.18263072394993 \times 10^{24} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.3652614478999 \times 10^{24} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 4.18263072394993 \times 10^{24} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \#1^8 \& , 4] \}, \\
\{v \rightarrow \text{Root}[2.72907296190758 \times 10^{92} m^4 + 1.99435302303285 \times 10^{79} z^2 - \\
& 5.45814592381516 \times 10^{92} m^2 z^2 + 2.72907296190758 \times 10^{92} z^4 + \\
& 2.04221749558564 \times 10^{82} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.45814592381516 \times 10^{92} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.99435302303285 \times 10^{79} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.09162918476303 \times 10^{93} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.45814592381516 \times 10^{92} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.08443499117128 \times 10^{82} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.72907296190758 \times 10^{92} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 5.45814592381516 \times 10^{92} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.72907296190758 \times 10^{92} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& (1.41707305305719 \times 10^{65} - 1.21460127361635 \times 10^{76} m^4 - \\
& 4.43803400573641 \times 10^{62} z^2 + 2.42920254723271 \times 10^{76} m^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.21460127361635 \times 10^{76} z^4 - 1.02128390341028 \times 10^{66} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.42920254723271 \times 10^{76} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.43803400573641 \times 10^{62} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.85840509446541 \times 10^{76} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.42920254723271 \times 10^{76} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.47573858559769 \times 10^{66} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.21460127361635 \times 10^{76} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.42920254723271 \times 10^{76} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.21460127361635 \times 10^{76} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \#1^2 + \\
& (-4.13670478075728 \times 10^{48} + 2.02713926275805 \times 10^{59} m^4 + \\
& 2.46898939262524 \times 10^{45} z^2 - 4.05427852551609 \times 10^{59} m^2 z^2 + \\
& 2.02713926275805 \times 10^{59} z^4 + 1.90750642610774 \times 10^{49} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.05427852551609 \times 10^{59} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.46898939262524 \times 10^{45} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.1085570510322 \times 10^{59} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.05427852551609 \times 10^{59} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.16033093991256 \times 10^{49} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.02713926275805 \times 10^{59} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 4.05427852551609 \times 10^{59} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.02713926275805 \times 10^{59} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \#1^4 + \\
 & (3.94244217957789 \times 10^{31} - 1.50366440955749 \times 10^{42} m^4 + \\
 & \quad 3.00732881911498 \times 10^{42} m^2 z^2 - 1.50366440955749 \times 10^{42} z^4 - \\
 & \quad 1.57697687183116 \times 10^{32} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.00732881911498 \times 10^{42} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 6.01465763822995 \times 10^{42} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.00732881911498 \times 10^{42} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 1.57697687183116 \times 10^{32} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.50366440955749 \times 10^{42} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 3.00732881911498 \times 10^{42} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.50366440955749 \times 10^{42} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \#1^6 + \\
 & (-1.21730575452964 \times 10^{14} + 4.18263072394993 \times 10^{24} m^4 - 8.3652614478999 \times 10^{24} \\
 & \quad m^2 z^2 + 4.18263072394993 \times 10^{24} z^4 + 4.86922301811856 \times 10^{14} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 8.3652614478999 \times 10^{24} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.67305228957997 \times 10^{25} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 8.3652614478999 \times 10^{24} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.86922301811856 \times 10^{14} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 4.18263072394993 \times 10^{24} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.3652614478999 \times 10^{24} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 4.18263072394993 \times 10^{24} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \#1^8 \&, 5\}], \\
 & \{v \rightarrow \text{Root}[2.72907296190758 \times 10^{92} m^4 + 1.99435302303285 \times 10^{79} z^2 - \\
 & \quad 5.45814592381516 \times 10^{92} m^2 z^2 + 2.72907296190758 \times 10^{92} z^4 + \\
 & \quad 2.04221749558564 \times 10^{82} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 5.45814592381516 \times 10^{92} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.99435302303285 \times 10^{79} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 1.09162918476303 \times 10^{93} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 5.45814592381516 \times 10^{92} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 4.08443499117128 \times 10^{82} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 2.72907296190758 \times 10^{92} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 5.45814592381516 \times 10^{92} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 2.72907296190758 \times 10^{92} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad (1.41707305305719 \times 10^{65} - 1.21460127361635 \times 10^{76} m^4 - \\
 & \quad \quad 4.43803400573641 \times 10^{62} z^2 + 2.42920254723271 \times 10^{76} m^2 z^2 - \\
 & \quad \quad 1.21460127361635 \times 10^{76} z^4 - 1.02128390341028 \times 10^{66} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad \quad 2.42920254723271 \times 10^{76} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.43803400573641 \times 10^{62} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad \quad 4.85840509446541 \times 10^{76} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.42920254723271 \times 10^{76} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad \quad 1.47573858559769 \times 10^{66} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.21460127361635 \times 10^{76} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad \quad 2.42920254723271 \times 10^{76} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.21460127361635 \times 10^{76} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \#1^2 + \\
 & (-4.13670478075728 \times 10^{48} + 2.02713926275805 \times 10^{59} m^4 + \\
 & \quad 2.46898939262524 \times 10^{45} z^2 - 4.05427852551609 \times 10^{59} m^2 z^2 + \\
 & \quad 2.02713926275805 \times 10^{59} z^4 + 1.90750642610774 \times 10^{49} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 4.05427852551609 \times 10^{59} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.46898939262524 \times 10^{45} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 8.1085570510322 \times 10^{59} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.05427852551609 \times 10^{59} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 2.16033093991256 \times 10^{49} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.02713926275805 \times 10^{59} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 4.05427852551609 \times 10^{59} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.02713926275805 \times 10^{59} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \#1^4 + \\
 & (3.94244217957789 \times 10^{31} - 1.50366440955749 \times 10^{42} m^4 + \\
 & \quad 3.00732881911498 \times 10^{42} m^2 z^2 - 1.50366440955749 \times 10^{42} z^4 - \\
 & \quad 1.57697687183116 \times 10^{32} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.00732881911498 \times 10^{42} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 6.01465763822995 \times 10^{42} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.00732881911498 \times 10^{42} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.57697687183116 \times 10^{32} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.50366440955749 \times 10^{42} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.00732881911498 \times 10^{42} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.50366440955749 \times 10^{42} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \#1^6 + \\
 & (-1.21730575452964 \times 10^{14} + 4.18263072394993 \times 10^{24} m^4 - 8.3652614478999 \times 10^{24} \\
 & m^2 z^2 + 4.18263072394993 \times 10^{24} z^4 + 4.86922301811856 \times 10^{14} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 8.3652614478999 \times 10^{24} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.67305228957997 \times 10^{25} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 8.3652614478999 \times 10^{24} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.86922301811856 \times 10^{14} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 4.18263072394993 \times 10^{24} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.3652614478999 \times 10^{24} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 4.18263072394993 \times 10^{24} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \#1^8 \& , 6 \} , \\
 \{v \rightarrow \text{Root} [& 2.72907296190758 \times 10^{92} m^4 + 1.99435302303285 \times 10^{79} z^2 - \\
 & 5.45814592381516 \times 10^{92} m^2 z^2 + 2.72907296190758 \times 10^{92} z^4 + \\
 & 2.04221749558564 \times 10^{82} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.45814592381516 \times 10^{92} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.99435302303285 \times 10^{79} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.09162918476303 \times 10^{93} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.45814592381516 \times 10^{92} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 4.08443499117128 \times 10^{82} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.72907296190758 \times 10^{92} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 5.45814592381516 \times 10^{92} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.72907296190758 \times 10^{92} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & (1.41707305305719 \times 10^{65} - 1.21460127361635 \times 10^{76} m^4 - \\
 & 4.43803400573641 \times 10^{62} z^2 + 2.42920254723271 \times 10^{76} m^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.21460127361635 \times 10^{76} z^4 - 1.02128390341028 \times 10^{66} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.42920254723271 \times 10^{76} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.43803400573641 \times 10^{62} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 4.85840509446541 \times 10^{76} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.42920254723271 \times 10^{76} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.47573858559769 \times 10^{66} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.21460127361635 \times 10^{76} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.42920254723271 \times 10^{76} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.21460127361635 \times 10^{76} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \#1^2 + \\
 & (-4.13670478075728 \times 10^{48} + 2.02713926275805 \times 10^{59} m^4 + \\
 & 2.46898939262524 \times 10^{45} z^2 - 4.05427852551609 \times 10^{59} m^2 z^2 + \\
 & 2.02713926275805 \times 10^{59} z^4 + 1.90750642610774 \times 10^{49} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 4.05427852551609 \times 10^{59} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.46898939262524 \times 10^{45} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.1085570510322 \times 10^{59} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.05427852551609 \times 10^{59} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.16033093991256 \times 10^{49} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.02713926275805 \times 10^{59} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 4.05427852551609 \times 10^{59} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.02713926275805 \times 10^{59} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \#1^4 + \\
 & (3.94244217957789 \times 10^{31} - 1.50366440955749 \times 10^{42} m^4 + \\
 & 3.00732881911498 \times 10^{42} m^2 z^2 - 1.50366440955749 \times 10^{42} z^4 - \\
 & 1.57697687183116 \times 10^{32} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.00732881911498 \times 10^{42} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 6.01465763822995 \times 10^{42} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.00732881911498 \times 10^{42} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.57697687183116 \times 10^{32} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.50366440955749 \times 10^{42} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.00732881911498 \times 10^{42} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.50366440955749 \times 10^{42} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \#1^6 + \\
 & (-1.21730575452964 \times 10^{14} + 4.18263072394993 \times 10^{24} m^4 - 8.3652614478999 \times 10^{24} \\
 & m^2 z^2 + 4.18263072394993 \times 10^{24} z^4 + 4.86922301811856 \times 10^{14} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 8.3652614478999 \times 10^{24} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.67305228957997 \times 10^{25} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 8.3652614478999 \times 10^{24} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.86922301811856 \times 10^{14} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 4.18263072394993 \times 10^{24} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.3652614478999 \times 10^{24} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 4.18263072394993 \times 10^{24} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \#1^8 \&, 7\}}, \\
 \{v \rightarrow \text{Root}[& 2.72907296190758 \times 10^{92} m^4 + 1.99435302303285 \times 10^{79} z^2 - \\
 & 5.45814592381516 \times 10^{92} m^2 z^2 + 2.72907296190758 \times 10^{92} z^4 + \\
 & 2.04221749558564 \times 10^{82} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.45814592381516 \times 10^{92} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.99435302303285 \times 10^{79} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.09162918476303 \times 10^{93} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.45814592381516 \times 10^{92} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 4.08443499117128 \times 10^{82} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.72907296190758 \times 10^{92} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 5.45814592381516 \times 10^{92} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.72907296190758 \times 10^{92} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & (1.41707305305719 \times 10^{65} - 1.21460127361635 \times 10^{76} m^4 - \\
 & 4.43803400573641 \times 10^{62} z^2 + 2.42920254723271 \times 10^{76} m^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.21460127361635 \times 10^{76} z^4 - 1.02128390341028 \times 10^{66} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.42920254723271 \times 10^{76} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.43803400573641 \times 10^{62} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 4.85840509446541 \times 10^{76} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.42920254723271 \times 10^{76} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.47573858559769 \times 10^{66} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.21460127361635 \times 10^{76} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.42920254723271 \times 10^{76} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.21460127361635 \times 10^{76} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \#1^2 + \\
 & (-4.13670478075728 \times 10^{48} + 2.02713926275805 \times 10^{59} m^4 + \\
 & 2.46898939262524 \times 10^{45} z^2 - 4.05427852551609 \times 10^{59} m^2 z^2 + \\
 & 2.02713926275805 \times 10^{59} z^4 + 1.90750642610774 \times 10^{49} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 4.05427852551609 \times 10^{59} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.46898939262524 \times 10^{45} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.1085570510322 \times 10^{59} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.05427852551609 \times 10^{59} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.16033093991256 \times 10^{49} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.02713926275805 \times 10^{59} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 4.05427852551609 \times 10^{59} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.02713926275805 \times 10^{59} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \#1^4 + \\
 & (3.94244217957789 \times 10^{31} - 1.50366440955749 \times 10^{42} m^4 + \\
 & 3.00732881911498 \times 10^{42} m^2 z^2 - 1.50366440955749 \times 10^{42} z^4 - \\
 & 1.57697687183116 \times 10^{32} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.00732881911498 \times 10^{42} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 6.01465763822995 \times 10^{42} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.00732881911498 \times 10^{42} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.57697687183116 \times 10^{32} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.50366440955749 \times 10^{42} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.00732881911498 \times 10^{42} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.50366440955749 \times 10^{42} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \#1^6 + \\
 & (-1.21730575452964 \times 10^{14} + 4.18263072394993 \times 10^{24} m^4 - 8.3652614478999 \times 10^{24} \\
 & m^2 z^2 + 4.18263072394993 \times 10^{24} z^4 + 4.86922301811856 \times 10^{14} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 8.3652614478999 \times 10^{24} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.67305228957997 \times 10^{25} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 8.3652614478999 \times 10^{24} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.86922301811856 \times 10^{14} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 4.18263072394993 \times 10^{24} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.3652614478999 \times 10^{24} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 4.18263072394993 \times 10^{24} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \#1^8 \&, 8\}}]
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{In[]:= Solve[m == 0.5 \sqrt{-((8. (4.493775893684088 * ^16 q^2 - 8.987551787368176 * ^16 q s +} \\
 4.493775893684088 * ^16 s^2 - 0.5 * q^2 v^2 + 1. * q s v^2 - 0.5 * s^2 v^2 -}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.493775893684088 \cdot z^2 + 0.5 \cdot v^2 z^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot q^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot q s \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot s^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1. \cdot q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2. \cdot q s v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1. \cdot s^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.493775893684088 \cdot z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 0.5 \cdot v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2) / \\
& (8.987551787368176 \cdot v^2 - 1. \cdot v^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& v^2 \sin[\beta]^2) + \\
2. \cdot \sqrt{ & ((16. \cdot (4.493775893684088 \cdot q^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot q s + \\
& 4.493775893684088 \cdot s^2 - 0.5 \cdot q^2 v^2 + 1. \cdot q s v^2 - \\
& 0.5 \cdot s^2 v^2 - 4.493775893684088 \cdot z^2 + 0.5 \cdot v^2 z^2 - \\
& 8.987551787368176 \cdot q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot q s \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot s^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1. \cdot q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2. \cdot q s v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1. \cdot s^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.493775893684088 \cdot z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 0.5 \cdot v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^2) / \\
& (8.987551787368176 \cdot v^2 - 1. \cdot v^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^2 - \\
(16. \cdot (& 2.0194021782656225 \cdot q^4 - 8.07760871306249 \cdot q^3 \\
& s + 1.2116413069593733 \cdot q^2 s^2 - 8.07760871306249 \cdot q^3 s^3 + 2.0194021782656225 \cdot q^4 s^4 - 4.493775893684088 \cdot q^4 \\
& v^2 + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot q^3 s v^2 - 2.6962655362104528 \cdot q^2 s^2 v^2 + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot q s^3 v^2 - 4.493775893684088 \cdot s^4 \\
& s^4 v^2 + 0.25 \cdot q^4 v^4 - 1. \cdot q^3 s v^4 + 1.5 \cdot q^2 s^2 v^4 - 1. \cdot q s^3 v^4 + 0.25 \cdot s^4 \\
& v^4 - 4.038804356531245 \cdot q^2 z^2 + 8.07760871306249 \cdot q^3 s z^2 - 4.038804356531245 \cdot s^2 z^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot q^2 v^2 \\
& z^2 - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot q s v^2 z^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot s^2 v^2 \\
& z^2 - 0.5 \cdot q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1. \cdot q s v^4 z^2 - 0.5 \cdot s^2 v^4 z^2 + 2.0194021782656225 \cdot q^3 \\
& z^4 - 4.493775893684088 \cdot q^2 v^2 z^4 + 0.25 \cdot v^4 z^4 - 8.07760871306249 \cdot q^3 \\
& q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.231043485224996 \cdot q^3 s \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.846565227837493 \cdot q^2 s^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.231043485224996 \cdot q^3 s^3 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.07760871306249 \cdot q^4 s^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot q^4 \\
& v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.190041429894541 \cdot q^3 s v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.0785062144841811 \cdot q^2 s^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.190041429894541 \cdot q^3 s^3 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.7975103574736352 \cdot q^4 s^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1. \cdot q^4 \\
& v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4. \cdot q^3 s v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6. \cdot q^2 s^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4. \cdot q s^3 v^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 - 1. \cdot s^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.038804356531245 \cdot q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.07760871306249 \cdot q^3 s z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.038804356531245 \cdot s^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.7975103574736352 \cdot q s v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot s^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 0.5 \cdot q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1. \cdot q s v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 0.5 \cdot s^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.038804356531245 \cdot q^3 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot q^2 v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 0.5 \cdot v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.07760871306249 \cdot q^3 \\
& q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 3.231043485224996 \cdot q^3 s \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.846565227837493 \cdot q^2 s^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 3.231043485224996 \cdot q^3 s^3 \sin[\beta]^4 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 8.07760871306249 \cdot 10^{33} s^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} \\
 & q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 7.190041429894541 \cdot 10^{17} q^3 s v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.0785062144841811 \cdot 10^{18} q^2 s^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 7.190041429894541 \cdot 10^{17} \\
 & q s^3 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} s^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1. \cdot 10^{17} q^4 \\
 & v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4. \cdot 10^{17} q^3 s v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 6. \cdot 10^{17} q^2 s^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4. \cdot 10^{17} q s^3 v^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 + 1. \cdot 10^{17} s^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.0194021782656225 \cdot 10^{33} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 4.493775893684088 \cdot 10^{16} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 0.25 \cdot 10^{17} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4) / \\
 & ((8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} - 1. \cdot 10^{17} v^2 - 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^2), s]
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 Out[] = & \left\{ \left\{ s \rightarrow - \frac{0.25 q (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4)}{2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4} - \right. \right. \\
 & 0.5 \sqrt{\left(\frac{0.25 q^2 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4)^2}{(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4)^2} - \right. \\
 & (0.666667 (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} \\
 & v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.08569 \times 10^{86} \\
 & q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
 & v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) / \\
& \left((8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \right. \\
& \left. (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \right) + \\
& (0.419974 (-3. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
& (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \\
& q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 \\
& v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 7.66115 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 7.14043 \times 10^{69}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} \\
 & q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \\
 & v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} \\
 & m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.36049 \times 10^{18} \\
 & q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \\
 & v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
 & v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} \\
 & v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} \\
 & q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 \\
 & v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} \\
 & m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} \\
 & v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} \\
& q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 + \\
12. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} \Big) \Big) / \\
& \left(\left((0. + 0. i) + 1.43146 \times 10^8 \cos[2. \beta] \right)^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. \right. \right.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
(27. & q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
& (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 - 9. q^2 \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
& (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + 2. \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^3 + 27. q^2 \\
 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^8 \\
 & (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4)^2 \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) - 72. \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) + \sqrt{(-4. \\
 & (-3. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 + 12.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
& \quad \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + \\
& \quad 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& \quad m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + \\
& \quad 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - \\
& \quad 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} \\
& \quad m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
& \quad 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& \quad m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
& \quad 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
& \quad 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& \quad q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + \\
& \quad 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& \quad 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \quad \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \\
& \quad z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} \\
& \quad m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& \quad 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& \quad 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
& \quad \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \\
& \quad z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& \quad q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} \\
& q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 \\
& v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 \\
& v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times \\
& 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 \\
& v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 \\
& q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
& m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} \\
& q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 \\
& v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} \\
& v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} \Big)^3 + \\
(27. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - \\
8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \\
2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 - 9. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - \\
 & 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 & (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
2. & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^3 + 27. q^2 \\
 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^8 \\
 & (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)^2 (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
 & q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 \\
 & v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
& v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
 & q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 \\
 & v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 \\
 & v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 72. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
& v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} \Big)^{1/3} \Big)^2 \Big)^{1/3} \Big)^4 + \\
 & \left(0.264567 \left(27. q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. \left(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 \right) \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \right. \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 - 9. q^2 \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
& (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2. \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^3 + 27. q^2 \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^8 \\
& (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)^2 \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) - 72. \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& \sqrt{\left(-4. \left(-3. q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right.\right.\right. \\
& \quad \left.\left.\left. v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2\right)^4 \left(-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right.\right.\right. \\
& \quad \left.\left.\left. 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4\right) \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - \right.\right.\right. \\
& \quad \left.\left.\left. 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - \right.\right.\right. \\
& \quad \left.\left.\left. 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \right.\right.\right. \\
& \quad \left.\left.\left. 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \right.\right.\right. \\
& \quad \left.\left.\left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \right.\right.\right. \\
& \quad \left.\left.\left. 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \right.\right.\right. \\
& \quad \left.\left.\left. 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right.\right.\right. \\
& \quad \left.\left.\left. 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right.\right.\right. \\
& \quad \left.\left.\left. 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right.\right.\right. \\
& \quad \left.\left.\left. 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right.\right.\right. \\
& \quad \left.\left.\left. 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right.\right.\right. \\
& \quad \left.\left.\left. 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right.\right.\right. \\
& \quad \left.\left.\left. 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right.\right.\right. \\
& \quad \left.\left.\left. 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \right.\right.\right. \\
& \quad \left.\left.\left. 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \right.\right.\right. \\
& \quad \left.\left.\left. 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \right.\right.\right. \\
& \quad \left.\left.\left. 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \right.\right.\right. \\
& \quad \left.\left.\left. 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \right.\right.\right. \\
& \quad \left.\left.\left. 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \right.\right.\right. \\
& \quad \left.\left.\left. 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \right.\right.\right. \\
& \quad \left.\left.\left. 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \right.\right.\right. \\
& \quad \left.\left.\left. 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \right.\right.\right. \\
& \quad \left.\left.\left. 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \right.\right.\right. \\
& \quad \left.\left.\left. 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \right.\right.\right. \\
& \quad \left.\left.\left. 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \right.\right.\right. \\
& \quad \left.\left.\left. 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \right.\right.\right. \\
& \quad \left.\left.\left. 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \right.\right.\right. \\
& \quad \left.\left.\left. 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \right.\right.\right. \\
& \quad \left.\left.\left. 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \right.\right.\right. \\
& \quad \left.\left.\left. 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \right.\right.\right. \\
& \quad \left.\left.\left. 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \right.\right.\right. \\
& \quad \left.\left.\left. 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \right.\right.\right. \\
& \quad \left.\left.\left. 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \right.\right.\right. \\
& \quad \left.\left.\left. 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \right.\right.\right. \\
& \quad \left.\left.\left. 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \right.\right.\right. \\
& \quad \left.\left.\left. 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \right.\right.\right.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) + \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 + 12. (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - \\
& 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} \\
& q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} \\
 & q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
 & q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} \\
& m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 \\
& v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 \\
& q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
& m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} \\
& q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} \\
& v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left. v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} \right)^3 + \\
 (27. & q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
 & (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
 & v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 - 9. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - \\
& 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
& (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
2. & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^3 + 27. q^2 \\
 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^8 \\
 & (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)^2 (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
 & v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
 & q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) - \\
72. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
 & q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 \\
 & v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
 & v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
 & q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} \Big)^2 \Big)^{1/3} \Big) / \\
 & \left(\left((0. + 0. i) + 1.43146 \times 10^8 \text{Cos}[2. \beta] \right)^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \right) \Big) -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$0.5 \sqrt{\left(\frac{0.5 q^2 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4)^2}{(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4)^2} \right)^2 -$$

(1.33333

$$\begin{aligned}
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) / \\
& \left((8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \right. \\
& \left. (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - \right. \\
& \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \\
& \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \right) - \\
& \left(0.419974 \left(-3. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left(-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) + \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 + \\
 12. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
& \quad 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
& \quad 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + \\
& \quad 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
& \quad 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& \quad 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + \\
& \quad 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
& \quad 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
& \quad 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& \quad 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& \quad 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& \quad 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& \quad 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + \\
& \quad 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
& \quad 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} \Big) \Big) / \\
& \left((0. + 0. i) + 1.43146 \times 10^8 \text{Cos}[2. \beta] \right)^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. \\
& v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (27. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
& (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 - 9. q^2 \\
 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 & (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + 2. \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^3 + 27. q^2 \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^8 \\
& (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4)^2 \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) - 72. \\
 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& \sqrt{-4. \left(-3. q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \left(-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4 \right) \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \right. \right.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 + 12. (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - \\
 & 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} \\
 & q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
 & q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} \\
& q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} \\
& m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 \\
& v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 \\
& q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
& m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} \\
& q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} \\
& v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} \Big)^3 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left(27. q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \right. \\
& \left(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 \right) \\
& \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \right. \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 - 9. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - \\
 & 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 & (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
 2. & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^3 + 27. q^2 \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^8 \\
& (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \\
& \sin[\beta]^4)^2 (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
& v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 \\
& \quad v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 \\
& \quad v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
72. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& \quad 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& \quad 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& \quad 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& \quad 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& \quad 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& \quad 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& \quad 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& \quad 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& \quad 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& \quad 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& \quad 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& \quad 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& \quad 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& \quad 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& \quad 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& \quad 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& \quad 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& \quad 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& \quad 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& \quad 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& \quad 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
 & q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} \Big)^{1/3} \Big) -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left(0.264567 \left(27. q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4 \right) \right. \\
 & \left. \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \right. \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 - 9. q^2 \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
& (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) + 2. \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^3 + 27. q^2 \\
 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^8 \\
 & (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)^2 \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) - 72. \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & \sqrt{-4. (-3. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4) (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - \\
 & \quad 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - \\
 & \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
 & \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
 & \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
 & \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & \quad 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 + 12. (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - \\
& 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} \\
& q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} \\
& q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 \\
 & z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 \\
 & v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
 & m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} \\
 & q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 \\
 & z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} \Big)^3 + \\
 & (27. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 & (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
 & v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 - 9. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - \\
& 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
2. & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^3 + 27. q^2 \\
 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^8 \\
 & (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)^2 (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
 & q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
 & v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
 & q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 \\
 & v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 \\
 & v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 72. (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
 & q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 \\
 & v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
 & q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} \Big) \Big) \Big) \Big) \Big) \Big)^{1/3} \Big) / \\
 & \left(\left((0. + 0. i) + 1.43146 \times 10^8 \text{Cos}[2. \beta] \right)^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \right) - \\
 & \left(0.25 \left(- \frac{1. q^3 \left(-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 \right)^3}{\left(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 \right)^3} - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left(8. q \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \left. \left. \left. 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 9.01595 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) / \\
& \left((8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \right. \\
& \left. (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) \right) +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& (4. \text{ q } (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{ Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} \text{ m}^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} \text{ q}^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \text{ m}^2 \text{ v}^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} \text{ q}^2 \text{ v}^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \text{ m}^2 \text{ v}^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} \text{ q}^2 \text{ v}^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \text{ m}^2 \text{ v}^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \text{ q}^2 \text{ v}^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \text{ m}^2 \text{ v}^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} \text{ q}^2 \text{ v}^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \text{ z}^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \text{ v}^2 \text{ z}^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \text{ v}^4 \text{ z}^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \text{ v}^6 \text{ z}^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \text{ v}^8 \text{ z}^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} \text{ m}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} \text{ q}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} \text{ m}^2 \text{ v}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} \text{ q}^2 \text{ v}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} \text{ m}^2 \text{ v}^4 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} \text{ q}^2 \text{ v}^4 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} \text{ m}^2 \text{ v}^6 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} \text{ q}^2 \text{ v}^6 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} \text{ m}^2 \text{ v}^8 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} \text{ q}^2 \text{ v}^8 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} \text{ z}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} \text{ v}^2 \text{ z}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} \text{ v}^4 \text{ z}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} \text{ v}^6 \text{ z}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} \text{ v}^8 \text{ z}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} \text{ m}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} \text{ q}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} \text{ m}^2 \text{ v}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} \text{ q}^2 \text{ v}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \text{ m}^2 \text{ v}^4 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} \text{ q}^2 \text{ v}^4 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \text{ m}^2 \text{ v}^6 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} \text{ q}^2 \text{ v}^6 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \text{ m}^2 \text{ v}^8 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} \text{ q}^2 \text{ v}^8 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} \text{ z}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} \text{ v}^2 \text{ z}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \text{ v}^4 \text{ z}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \text{ v}^6 \text{ z}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \text{ v}^8 \text{ z}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} \text{ m}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} \text{ q}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} \text{ m}^2 \text{ v}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} \text{ q}^2 \text{ v}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} \text{ m}^2 \text{ v}^4 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} \text{ q}^2 \text{ v}^4 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} \text{ m}^2 \text{ v}^6 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} \text{ q}^2 \text{ v}^6 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} \text{ m}^2 \text{ v}^8 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} \text{ q}^2 \text{ v}^8 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} \text{ z}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} \text{ v}^2 \text{ z}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \text{ v}^4 \text{ z}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \text{ v}^6 \text{ z}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \text{ v}^8 \text{ z}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} \text{ m}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} \text{ q}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} \text{ m}^2 \text{ v}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} \text{ q}^2 \text{ v}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} \text{ m}^2 \text{ v}^4 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} \text{ q}^2 \text{ v}^4 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} \text{ m}^2 \text{ v}^6 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} \text{ q}^2 \text{ v}^6 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} \text{ m}^2 \text{ v}^8 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} \text{ q}^2 \text{ v}^8 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} \text{ z}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} \text{ v}^2 \text{ z}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} \text{ v}^4 \text{ z}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} \text{ v}^6 \text{ z}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} \text{ v}^8 \text{ z}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} \text{ m}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} \text{ q}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} \text{ m}^2 \text{ v}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} \text{ q}^2 \text{ v}^2 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} \text{ m}^2 \text{ v}^4 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} \text{ q}^2 \text{ v}^4 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} \text{ m}^2 \text{ v}^6 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} \text{ q}^2 \text{ v}^6 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} \text{ m}^2 \text{ v}^8 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} \text{ q}^2 \text{ v}^8 \text{ Sin}[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) / \\
 & \left((8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \right. \\
 & \left. (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)^2 \right) \Bigg) / \\
 & \left(\sqrt{\left(\frac{0.25 q^2 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)^2}{(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)^2} \right.} \right. \\
 & \left. (0.666667 (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - \right. \\
 & \quad 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + \\
 & \quad 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
 & \quad 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + \\
 & \quad 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - \\
 & \quad 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
 & \quad 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & \quad 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & \quad 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) / \\
 & \left((8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \right. \\
 & \left. (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \right. \\
 & \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) \right) + (0.419974 \\
 & (-3. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
 & (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 + \\
12. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} \Big) \Big) / \\
 & \left((0. + 0. i) + 1.43146 \times 10^8 \text{Cos}[2. \beta] \right)^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - \right. \\
 & \quad \left. 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \\
 & \left(27. q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \right. \\
 & \quad \left(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 \right) \\
 & \quad \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \right. \\
 & \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
 & \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
 & \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
 & \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & \quad 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 - 9. q^2 \\
 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 & (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
2. & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^3 + 27. q^2 \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^8 \\
& (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4)^2 \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) - \\
 & 72. (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & \sqrt{\left(-4. \left(-3. q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \left(-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 \right) \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.06262 \times 10^{35} \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.73742 \times \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.34792 \times 10^{85} \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.9724 \times \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} \right. \right. \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 9.01595 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.58896 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times \\
& 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times \\
& 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
 & v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
 & v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} \\
 & v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times \\
 & 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
 & v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} \\
 & q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.42809 \times \\
 & 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} \\
 & v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 + \\
 12. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} \\
& m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} \\
& v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} \\
& m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} \\
& m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} \\
& m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times \\
& 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} \\
& m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} \\
& m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
& m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
& m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} \Big)^3 + \\
& \left(27. q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \left(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4 \right) \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} \right. \right.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times \\
& 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.73742 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} \\
& q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.62868 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.2081 \times \\
& 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.61816 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 9.01595 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} \\
& q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.52058 \times \\
& 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 - \\
9. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \\
\text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - \\
5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \\
q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \\
2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
\text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.06262 \times 10^{35} \\
m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.73742 \times \\
10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
\text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} \\
m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \\
\text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 \\
z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
\text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} \\
q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
 & v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.36964 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} \\
 & q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
 & v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times \\
 & 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} \\
 & v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 \\
 & v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times \\
 & 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times \\
 & 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times \\
& 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times \\
& 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times \\
& 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times \\
& 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.76796 \times \\
& 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2. (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times \\
& 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times \\
& 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times \\
& 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} \\
& q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.42809 \times \\
& 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^3 + \\
27. & q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^8 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4)^2 \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
& m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
& q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} \\
& v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
 & v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} \\
 & m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
 & q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} \\
 & v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 \\
 & v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.36964 \times \\
 & 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times \\
 & 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times \\
 & 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} \\
& q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times \\
& 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 \\
& v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times \\
& 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} \\
& m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} \\
& m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} \\
& q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times \\
& 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
 & v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) - \\
 72. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} \\
 & q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 v^8 + 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times \\
 & 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times \\
 & 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times \\
 & 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times \\
 & 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times \\
& 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.76796 \times \\
& 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} \left(1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + \right. \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
& m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
& q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} \\
& v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 \\
& v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.36964 \times \\
& 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times \\
& 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times \\
& 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} \\
& q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times \\
& 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 \\
& v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times \\
& 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} \\
& m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} \\
& m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} \\
& q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times \\
& 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
 & v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} \Big)^{2/3} \Big)^{1/3} + \\
 & \left(0.264567 \left(27. q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \left(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4 \right) \right. \\
 & \left. \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
 & \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
 & \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
 & \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & \quad 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & \quad 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & \quad 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & \quad 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & \quad 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & \quad 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & \quad 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & \quad 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & \quad 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & \quad 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 - 9. q^2 \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
& (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
2. & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^3 + 27. q^2 \\
 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^8 \\
 & (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4)^2 \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
72. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) + \\
 & \sqrt{(-4. (-3. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \\
 & \quad \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - \\
 & \quad 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \\
 & \quad q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
 & \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times \\
 & \quad 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \\
 & \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
 & \quad v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.06262 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.60437 \times 10^{86} \\
& m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 7.14043 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} \\
& q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 9.01595 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.58896 \times 10^{52} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 \\
 & z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) + \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
 & v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times \\
 & 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} \\
 & v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times \\
 & 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
 & v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
 & v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times \\
& 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} \\
& q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.42809 \times \\
& 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 + \\
12. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} \\
& m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} \\
& v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} \\
& m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} \\
& m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times \\
& 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} \\
& m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} \\
 & m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
 & m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
 & m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} \\
 & q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
 & v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} \Big)^3 + \\
 & \left(27. q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \left(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 \right) \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.73742 \times 10^{17} \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} \right. \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} \\
& q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.62868 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.2081 \times \\
& 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.61816 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 9.01595 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} \\
& q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.52058 \times \\
& 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 - \\
& 9. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
& q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} \\
& v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.36964 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} \\
& q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
& v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times \\
& 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 \\
& v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times \\
& 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times \\
& 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times \\
& 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times \\
& 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times \\
 & 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times \\
 & 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.76796 \times \\
 & 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} \\
 & v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2. (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
 & v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times \\
 & 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} \\
 & v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times \\
 & 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times \\
& 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} \\
& q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.42809 \times \\
& 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^3 + \\
& 27. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^8 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)^2 \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
& m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
& q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} \\
& v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times \\
& 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 \\
 & v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
 & q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
 & v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
 & v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} \\
 & m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} \\
 & q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times \\
 & 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
 & v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) - \\
 72. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} \\
 & q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 v^8 + 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times \\
& 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times \\
& 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times \\
& 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times \\
& 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times \\
& 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} \\
 & v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} \\
 & q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
 & q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} \\
 & v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 \\
 & v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
 & v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} \\
 & v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 \\
 & v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
 & q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
 & v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
 & v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} \\
 & m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} \\
 & q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times \\
 & 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
 & v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} \Big)^2 \Big)^{1/3} \Big) / \\
 & \left(\left((0. + 0. i) + 1.43146 \times 10^8 \cos[2. \beta] \right)^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - \right. \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
& v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.14917 \times 10^{36} \\
& q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} \\
& q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
& v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} \\
& q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} \\
& q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
& v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.81216 \times 10^{36} \\
& q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} \\
& q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} \\
 & m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
 & v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
 & z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
 & v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} \\
 & m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} \\
 & z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} \\
 & v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} \\
 & v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. \\
 & v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} \Big) / \\
 & \left((8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \right. \\
 & \left. (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - \right. \\
 & \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \\
 & \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \right. \\
 & \left. \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \right) + \\
 & \left(0.419974 \left(-3. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \right. \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) + \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 + \\
 12. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} \Big) \Big) \Big) /
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left((0. + 0. i) + 1.43146 \times 10^8 \operatorname{Cos}[2. \beta] \right)^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. \right. \\
& \quad \left. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \\
& \left(27. q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \right. \\
& \quad \left(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \\
& \quad \quad \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 \right) \\
& \quad \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \right. \\
& \quad \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - \\
& \quad \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
& \quad \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
& \quad \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \\
& \quad \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
& \quad \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& \quad \quad 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad \quad 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad \quad 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad \quad 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad \quad 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad \quad 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad \quad 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad \quad 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad \quad 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& \quad \quad 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad \quad 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& \quad \quad 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad \quad 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& \quad \quad 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& \quad \quad 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& \quad \quad 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& \quad \quad 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& \quad \quad 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& \quad \quad 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& \quad \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& \quad \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& \quad \quad 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& \quad \quad 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& \quad \quad 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& \quad \quad 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& \quad \quad 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& \quad \quad 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& \quad \quad 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 - 9. q^2 \\
 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
 & (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} \\
 & q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 6.18837 \times 10^{69} \\
 & q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19172 \times 10^{53} \\
& m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 \\
& v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
& v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
& v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2. \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^3 + 27. q^2 \\
 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^8 \\
 & (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4)^2 \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
 & v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
 & v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 \\
 & z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
 & z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
& m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) - 72. \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
 & v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
 & v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
 & v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
 & v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
& z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
& m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& \sqrt{-4. (-3. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4) (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) + \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 + 12. \\
 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
 & q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
& \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \\
& z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^2 v^6 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 \\
& v^6 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \\
 & z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} \\
 & m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 \\
 & z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 \\
 & v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
 & m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} \\
 & q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 \\
 & z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} \Big)^3 + \\
 & (27. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 - \\
 9. & q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
 & (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) + \\
 2. & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^3 + \\
27. & q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^8 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4)^2 \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
& v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 \\
 & \quad v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 \\
 & \quad v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 72. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 &7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
 &v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 &2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 &1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 &3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 &2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 &3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 &1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 &2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 &4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 &1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 &4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 &1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 &7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
 &\text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
 &q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 &1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 &4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 &3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 &4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 &1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 &5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 &2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 &9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 &3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 &2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 &2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 &8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 &1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 &5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 &\text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 &m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 &4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 &1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 &9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 &2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2)^{1/3}) +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\left(0.264567 \left(27. q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \right. \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \left(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 \right) \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \right. \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \left. 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - \right. \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 - 9. q^2 \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
& (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 6.18837 \times 10^{69} \\
& q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19172 \times 10^{53} \\
& m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 \\
 & v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
 & z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
 & v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
& v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2. \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^3 + 27. q^2 \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^8 \\
& (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)^2 \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
& z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
 & m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 \\
 & z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \\
 & z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) - 72. \\
 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} \\
& \quad q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
& \quad v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
 & v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 \\
 & z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
 & z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
 & m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 \\
 & z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \\
 & z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) + \\
 & \sqrt{(-4. (-3. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 + 12. \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} \\
& m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 \\
& v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
& m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} \\
& q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 \\
& z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} \Big)^3 + \\
(27. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - \\
8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + \\
5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 - \\
9. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
& (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
2. & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^3 + \\
 27. & q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^8 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4)^2 \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 \\
& \quad v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
& v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
72. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 \\
 & v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
 & q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} \Big)^{1/3} \Big) / \\
 & \left((0. + 0. i) + 1.43146 \times 10^8 \text{Cos}[2. \beta] \right)^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - \right. \\
 & \left. 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \Big) + \\
 & 0.5 \sqrt{\left(\frac{0.5 q^2 \left(-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 \right)^2}{\left(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 \right)^2} - \right. \\
 & \left. (1.33333 \right. \\
 & \left. (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + \right. \\
 & \left. 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - \right. \\
 & \left. 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \right. \\
 & \left. 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
& v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} \\
& q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} \\
& v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
& v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.14917 \times 10^{36} \\
& q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} \\
& q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \\
& v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
& v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} \\
& q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} \\
& q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
& v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.81216 \times 10^{36} \\
& q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} \\
& q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} \\
 & m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} \\
 & z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} \\
 & v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} \\
 & v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. \\
 & v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} \Big) / \\
 & \left((8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \right. \\
 & \left. (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - \right. \\
 & \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \\
 & \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \right) - \\
 & (0.419974 (-3. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 & (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 + \\
12. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} \Big) \Big) / \\
 & \left((0. + 0. i) + 1.43146 \times 10^8 \cos[2. \beta] \right)^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. \\
 & \quad v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & \left(27. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \right. \\
 & \quad (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
 & \quad (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
 & \quad \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - \\
 & \quad \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
 & \quad \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
 & \quad \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \\
 & \quad \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
 & \quad \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & \quad \quad 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad \quad 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad \quad 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad \quad 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad \quad 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad \quad 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad \quad 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad \quad 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad \quad 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad \quad 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad \quad 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad \quad \left. 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 - 9. q^2 \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
& (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} \\
& \quad q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 9.01595 \times 10^{17} \\
& \quad m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
& \quad z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
& \quad v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} \\
(& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
 & v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + 2. \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^3 + 27. q^2 \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^8 \\
& (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)^2 \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
 & v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & z^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
 & m^2 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 \\
 & z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \\
 & z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) - 72. \\
 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} \\
& \quad q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.76796 \times 10^{35} \\
& \quad q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
 & \quad v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 \\
 & \quad z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \\
 & \quad \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
 & \quad z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
 & \quad m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 \\
 & \quad z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \\
 & \quad z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) + \\
 & \sqrt{(-4. (-3. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 + 12. \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
& q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
& q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} \\
& q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
 & q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} \\
 & m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 \\
 & v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
 & m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} \\
 & q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 \\
 & z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12})^3 + \\
 & (27. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
 & (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 - \\
 9. & q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 & (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
2. & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^3 + \\
 27. & q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^8 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4)^2 \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
 & v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
 & q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 \\
 & v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 \\
 & v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) - \\
 72. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 \\
 & v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
 & q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} \Big)^{1/3} - \\
 & \left(0.264567 \left(27. q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. + (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. - (5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \right. \right. \\
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 - 9. q^2 \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
& (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} \\
& \quad q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 9.01595 \times 10^{17} \\
& \quad m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
& \quad z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
 & v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) + 2. \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^3 + 27. q^2 \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^8 \\
& (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)^2 \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 \\
 & z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
 & v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \\
 & z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
 & z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
 & m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 \\
 & z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \\
 & z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) - 72. \\
 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} \\
& \quad q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.76796 \times 10^{35} \\
& \quad q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
 & \quad v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 \\
 & \quad z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \\
 & \quad \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
 & \quad z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
 & \quad m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 \\
 & \quad z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \\
 & \quad z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
 & \sqrt{(-4. (-3. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4) (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 + 12. \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
& q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
& q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} \\
& q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
 & q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} \\
 & m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 \\
 & z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 \\
 & v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
 & m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} \\
 & q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 \\
 & z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} \Big)^3 + \\
 (27. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - \\
 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + \\
 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 - \\
 & 9. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
 & \quad 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 & (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) + \\
2. & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^3 + \\
 27. & q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^8 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4)^2 \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
 & v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
 & q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 \\
 & v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 \\
 & v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 72. (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 \\
 & v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
& v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
 & q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} \Big)^{1/3} \Big) / \\
 & \left((0. + 0. i) + 1.43146 \times 10^8 \text{Cos}[2. \beta] \right)^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - \right. \\
 & \quad \left. 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right)^4 - \\
 & \left(0.25 \left(- \frac{1. q^3 \left(-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 \right)^3}{\left(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 \right)^3} - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. (8. q \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - \\
 & \quad \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
 & \quad \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - \\
 & \quad \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + \\
 & \quad \quad 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
 & \quad \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + \\
 & \quad \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad \quad 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad \quad 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad \quad 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad \quad \left. \left. \left. 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19172 \times 10^{53} \\
& m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} \\
& q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 9.01595 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
& v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} \Big) /
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left((8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \right. \\
& \quad \left(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \\
& \quad \quad \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 \right) + \\
(4. q & \left(-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 \right) \\
& \quad \left(2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - \right. \\
& \quad \quad 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + \\
& \quad \quad 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& \quad \quad 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + \\
& \quad \quad 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - \\
& \quad \quad 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& \quad \quad 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - \\
& \quad \quad 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad \quad 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad \quad 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad \quad 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad \quad 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad \quad 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad \quad 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad \quad 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad \quad 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& \quad \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& \quad \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad \quad 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad \quad 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad \quad 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& \quad \quad 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& \quad \quad 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& \quad \quad 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& \quad \quad 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& \quad \quad 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& \quad \quad 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& \quad \quad 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& \quad \quad 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& \quad \quad 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& \quad \quad 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& \quad \quad 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& \quad \quad 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& \quad \quad 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& \quad \quad 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& \quad \quad 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& \quad \quad 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) / \\
 & \left((8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \right. \\
 & \left. (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)^2 \right) \Bigg) / \\
 & \left(\sqrt{\left(\frac{0.25 q^2 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)^2}{(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)^2} \right.} \right. \\
 & \left. (0.666667 (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - \right. \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \left. \left. 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} \\
 & \quad m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
 & \quad m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) / \\
 & \left((8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \right. \\
 & \quad (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \right) + (0.419974 \\
 & \quad (-3. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & \quad (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 & \quad (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
 & \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
 & \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - \\
 & \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
(& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 + \\
12. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} \Big) \Big) \Big) \Big) \Big) /
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left(\left((0. + 0. i) + 1.43146 \times 10^8 \text{Cos}[2. \beta] \right)^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \right. \\
& \left(27. q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \right. \\
& \quad \left(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 \right) \\
& \quad \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \right. \\
& \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
& \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
& \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
& \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& \quad 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad \left. \left. 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \right.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 - 9. q^2 \\
 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
2. & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^3 + 27. q^2 \\
 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^8 \\
 & (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)^2 \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 72. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) + \\
 & \sqrt{\left(-4. \left(-3. q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \left(-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 \right) \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.06262 \times 10^{35} \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.60437 \times 10^{86} \right. \right. \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 7.14043 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} \\
& q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 9.01595 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.58896 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times \\
& 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times \\
& 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times \\
& 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.42809 \times \\
& 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} \Big)^2 + \\
12. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} \\
& m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} \\
& v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} \\
 & m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
 & q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} \\
 & m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} \\
 & m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
 & q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
 & v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} \\
& m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times \\
& 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} \\
& m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} \\
& m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
& m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
& m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left(\text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \right. \\
 & \left. v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} \right)^3 + \\
 (27. q^2 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \\
 & q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} \\
 & v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times \\
 & 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.73742 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
 & v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
 & v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} \\
 & q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
 & v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.62868 \times 10^{53} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.2081 \times
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.61816 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 9.01595 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} \\
& q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.52058 \times \\
& 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 - \\
& 9. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \\
& q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.06262 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.73742 \times \\
& 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
 & v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
 & v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.36964 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} \\
 & q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
 & v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times \\
 & 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} \\
 & v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 \\
 & v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times \\
 & 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times \\
& 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times \\
& 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times \\
& 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times \\
& 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times \\
& 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.76796 \times \\
& 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2. (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times \\
& 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times \\
& 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times \\
& 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} \\
& q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.42809 \times \\
& 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^3 + \\
& 27. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^8 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)^2 \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
& m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
& q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} \\
& v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 \\
 & v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
 & v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} \\
 & m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
 & q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} \\
 & v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 \\
 & v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.36964 \times \\
 & 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times \\
 & 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times \\
& 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} \\
& q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times \\
& 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 \\
& v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times \\
& 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} \\
& m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} \\
& m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} \\
 & q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times \\
 & 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
 & v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12}) - \\
 72. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} \\
 & q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 v^8 + 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times \\
 & 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times \\
 & 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times \\
& 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times \\
& 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.76796 \times \\
& 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} \left(1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + \right. \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
& m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
& q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} \\
& v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 \\
 & v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
 & v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} \\
 & m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
 & q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} \\
 & v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 \\
 & v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.36964 \times \\
 & 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times \\
& 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} \\
& q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times \\
& 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 \\
& v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times \\
& 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} \\
& m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} \\
 & q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times \\
 & 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
 & v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} \Big)^{2/3} \Big)^{1/3} + \\
 & \left(0.264567 \left(27. q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \left(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 \right) \right. \\
 & \left. \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
 & \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
 & \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
 & \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & \quad 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & \quad 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 - 9. q^2 \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
& (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2. & \left(2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \right. \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^3 + 27. q^2 \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^8 \\
& (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)^2 \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12}) - \\
72. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
& \sqrt{\left(-4. \left(-3. q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2\right)^4 \left(-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4\right) \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.06262 \times 10^{35} \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.34792 \times 10^{85} \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.9724 \times \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} \right. \right. \right.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times \\
 & 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
 & v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 9.01595 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
 & v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.58896 \times 10^{52} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
 & v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times \\
 & 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} \\
 & v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times \\
 & 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times \\
& 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} \\
& q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.42809 \times \\
& 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 + \\
& 12. (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} \\
& m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} \\
& v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} \\
& m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} \\
& m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} \\
 & m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
 & q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} \\
 & v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} \\
 & m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
 & m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
 & m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} \\
 & q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
 & v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} \Big)^3 + \\
 & \left(27. q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \left(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4 \right) \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - \right. \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} \\
& v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times \\
& 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.73742 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} \\
& q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.62868 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.2081 \times \\
& 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.61816 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 9.01595 \times 10^{17}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \\
 & v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} \\
 & q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.52058 \times \\
 & 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} \\
 & v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 - \\
 9. q^2 (& 8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
 (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
 & q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.06262 \times 10^{35} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.73742 \times \\
 & 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
 & v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.36964 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} \\
& q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
& v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times \\
& 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 \\
& v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times \\
& 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times \\
& 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times \\
 & 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times \\
 & 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times \\
 & 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times \\
 & 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.76796 \times \\
 & 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} \\
 & v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2. (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times \\
& 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times \\
& 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times \\
& 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
 & v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} \\
 & q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.42809 \times \\
 & 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} \\
 & v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^3 + \\
 & 27. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^8 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4)^2 \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
 & m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
 & q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} \\
 & v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 \\
 & v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
 & m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} \\
 & m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times \\
 & 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} \\
 & v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 \\
 & v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
 & q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
 & v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
 & v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} \\
 & m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} \\
 & q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) - \\
72. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} \\
& q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 v^8 + 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times \\
& 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times \\
& 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times \\
& 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times \\
 & 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} \\
 & q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
 & v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times \\
 & 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} \\
 & v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} \\
 & q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
 & q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} \\
 & v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times \\
& 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 \\
& v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
& v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} \\
& m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} \\
& q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} \\
& q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
& v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.14917 \times 10^{36} \\
& q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} \\
& q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
& v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} \\
& q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} \\
& q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
& v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.81216 \times 10^{36} \\
& q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} \\
& q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} \\
& m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} \Big) \Big) /
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left((8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \right. \\
 & \quad (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - \\
 & \quad \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
 & \quad \quad \left. \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 \right) + \\
 & (0.419974 (-3. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
 & \quad 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 & \quad (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
 & \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - \\
 & \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
 & \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
 & \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - \\
 & \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
 & \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + \\
 & \quad 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
 & \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + \\
 & \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & \quad 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 + \\
 12. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} \Big) \Big) / \\
& \left((0. + 0. i) + 1.43146 \times 10^8 \cos[2. \beta] \right)^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. \\
& \quad v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& \left(27. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \right. \\
& \quad (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
& \quad (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
& \quad \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - \\
& \quad \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
& \quad \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
& \quad \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \\
& \quad \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
& \quad \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& \quad \quad 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad \quad 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad \quad 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad \quad 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad \quad 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad \quad 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad \quad 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad \quad 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad \quad 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& \quad \quad 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad \quad 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& \quad \quad \left. 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \right)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 - 9. q^2 \\
 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
 & (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} \\
& \quad q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} \\
& \quad q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
& \quad v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} \\
& \quad q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
& \quad v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} \\
& \quad m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
 & \quad z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} \\
 & \quad q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} \\
 & \quad q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} \\
& \quad q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} \\
& \quad q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) + 2. \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^3 + 27. q^2 \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^8 \\
& (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4)^2 \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
 & \quad z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) - 72. \\
 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & \quad 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & \quad 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} \\
& \quad q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} \\
& \quad q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} \\
& \quad q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} \\
& \quad q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
 & v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
 & v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
& \quad z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) + \\
 & \sqrt{(-4. (-3. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - \\
 & \quad 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - \\
 & \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
 & \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
 & \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
 & \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & \quad 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & \quad 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & \quad 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & \quad 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & \quad 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & \quad 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & \quad 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & \quad 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & \quad 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & \quad 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & \quad 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & \quad 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & \quad 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 + 12. \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \\
 & z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} \\
 & m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
 & q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
 & q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
 & v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
 & q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
 & v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 \\
 & v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} \Big)^3 + \\
(27. & q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
& (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 - \\
 9. & q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 & (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) + \\
 2. & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^3 + \\
27. & q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^8 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)^2 \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
& v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 \\
 & \quad v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 \\
 & \quad v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 72. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
 & \quad v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
 & \quad \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
 & \quad q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \quad \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & \quad m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} \Big)^2 \Big)^{1/3} \Big)^+
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\left(0.264567 \left(27. q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \right. \right.$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
 & (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
 & \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - \\
 & \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
 & \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
 & \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \\
 & \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
 & \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & \quad 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & \quad 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & \quad 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & \quad 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & \quad 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & \quad 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & \quad 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & \quad 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & \quad 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & \quad 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & \quad 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & \quad 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & \quad 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & \quad 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 - 9. q^2 \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
& (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \\
 & v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) + 2. \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^3 + 27. q^2 \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^8 \\
& (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)^2 \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& \quad z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
& \quad v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& \quad v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \quad \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& \quad z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& \quad v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \quad \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
& z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) - 72. \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} \\
 & \quad q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} \\
 & \quad m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & \quad 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & \quad 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + \\
 & \quad 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \quad \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
 & \quad z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
 & \quad v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
 & \quad v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \quad \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
 & \quad z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
 & \quad v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \quad \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
 & \quad z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
& \quad z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) + \\
 & \sqrt{(-4. (-3. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - \\
 & \quad 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - \\
 & \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
 & \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
 & \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
 & \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & \quad 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & \quad 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & \quad 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & \quad 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & \quad 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & \quad 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) + \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 + 12. \\
 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
 & q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} \\
 & m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
 & q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
 & q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
 & v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
 & q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 \\
& z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} \Big)^3 + \\
(27. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - \\
8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + \\
5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 - \\
 9. & q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
 & (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) + \\
 2. & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^3 + \\
 27. & q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^8 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)^2 \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 \\
 & v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
 & q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 \\
 & v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 \\
 & v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 72. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 \\
 & \quad v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left(\left(\left(\left(\left(\left(m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \right. \right. \right. \right. \right. \right. \right. \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & \left. \left. \left. \left. \left. \left. \left. 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} \right)^2 \right)^{1/3} \right)^2 \right)^2 \right)^2 \right)^2 \right)^2 \\
 & \left(\left((0. + 0. i) + 1.43146 \times 10^8 \cos[2. \beta] \right)^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \right) \left. \right) - \\
 & 0.5 \sqrt{\left(\frac{0.5 q^2 \left(-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4 \right)^2}{\left(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4 \right)^2} - \right.} \\
 & \left. \left(1.33333 \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left(2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} \\
 & q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} \\
 & q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} \\
 & q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} \\
 & v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} \\
& v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
& v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.14917 \times 10^{36} \\
& q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} \\
& q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \\
& v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
& v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} \\
& q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} \\
& q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \\
& v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
& v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.81216 \times 10^{36} \\
& q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} \\
& q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} \\
 & v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} \\
 & m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
 & v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
 & v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} \\
 & m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} \\
 & v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} \\
 & v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. \\
 & v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} \Big) / \\
 & \left((8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \right. \\
 & \left. (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - \right. \\
 & \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \right. \\
 & \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) \right) - \\
 & \left(0.419974 \left(-3. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left(-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4) \right) \right. \\
 & \left. (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \right. \\
 & \left. 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 + \\
12. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left(\left((0. + 0. i) + 1.43146 \times 10^8 \cos[2. \beta] \right)^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \right. \\
 & \left(27. q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \right. \\
 & \quad \left(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \right. \\
 & \quad \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4 \right) \\
 & \quad \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \right. \\
 & \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - \\
 & \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
 & \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
 & \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \\
 & \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
 & \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & \quad 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & \quad 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & \quad 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & \quad 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & \quad 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & \quad 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & \quad \left. 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 - 9. q^2 \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
& (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 6.18837 \times 10^{69} \\
& q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19172 \times 10^{53} \\
 & m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 \\
 & v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
 & v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} \\
& \quad q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& \quad m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} \\
& \quad m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} \\
& \quad m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
 & v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2. \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^3 + 27. q^2 \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^8 \\
& (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)^2 \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 &1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 &5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 &2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 &1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 &1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
 &v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 &1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 &\sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 &7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
 &z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 &8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 &5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
 &v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 &2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 &3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 &2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 &1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 &3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 &2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 &2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 &1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 &8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 &5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 &2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
 &v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 &2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 &\sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 &1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
 &z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 &2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 &1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
 &v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 &2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 &5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 &3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 &2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 &5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 &4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 &4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 &3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 &1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 &9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 &2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
 & z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
 & m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12}) - 72. \\
 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
& v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
& z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
& m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) + \\
& \sqrt{(-4. (-3. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - \\
& \quad 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - \\
& \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
& \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
& \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
& \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& \quad 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& \quad 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& \quad 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& \quad 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& \quad 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& \quad 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& \quad 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& \quad 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& \quad 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& \quad 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& \quad 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& \quad 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& \quad 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& \quad 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& \quad 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& \quad 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& \quad 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& \quad 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& \quad 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 + 12. \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
 & q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
 & v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 \\
 & v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} \\
& m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 \\
& v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
& m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} \\
& q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} \Big)^3 + \\
 (27. & q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
 & (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 - \\
9. q^2 (& 8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
(& -5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
2. & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^3 + \\
 27. & q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^8 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)^2 \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
& v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 \\
& \quad v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 \\
& \quad v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
72. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
 & v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
 & q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} \Big)^2 \Big)^{1/3} \Big) -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\left(0.264567 \left(27. q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \right. \right.$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
& (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
& \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - \\
& \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
& \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
& \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \\
& \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
& \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& \quad 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& \quad 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& \quad 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& \quad 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& \quad 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& \quad 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& \quad 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& \quad 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& \quad 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& \quad 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& \quad 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& \quad 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& \quad 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& \quad 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& \quad 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& \quad 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& \quad 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& \quad 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& \quad 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& \quad 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 - 9. q^2 \\
 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
 & (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} \\
 & q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 6.18837 \times 10^{69} \\
 & q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19172 \times 10^{53} \\
 & m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 \\
& v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
& v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
& v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2. \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^3 + 27. q^2 \\
 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^8 \\
 & (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)^2 \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
 & v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& \quad v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
& \quad v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 \\
& \quad z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \\
& \quad \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
& \quad z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
& m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) - 72. \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} \\
 & \quad m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} \\
 & \quad q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
 & \quad v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & \quad 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & \quad 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + \\
 & \quad 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
 & \quad 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & \quad 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + \\
 & \quad 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
 & \quad 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
 & v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
 & v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
 & v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
& z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
& m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) + \\
& \sqrt{(-4. (-3. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 + 12. \\
 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
 & q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \\
 & z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} \\
 & m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 \\
 & v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
 & m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} \\
 & q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 \\
 & z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12})^3 + \\
 & (27. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
 & (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 - \\
 9. & q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 & (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) + \\
 2. & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^3 + \\
27. & q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^8 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4)^2 \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 \\
 & v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 \\
 & v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 72. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
 & q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} \Big)^{1/3} \Big) / \\
 & \left(((0. + 0. i) + 1.43146 \times 10^8 \text{Cos}[2. \beta])^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - \right. \\
 & \quad \left. 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \right) + \\
 & \left(0.25 \left(- \frac{1. q^3 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)^3}{(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)^3} - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left(8. q (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - \\
 & \quad \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
 & \quad \quad \left. \left. 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - \right. \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.06262 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19172 \times 10^{53} \\
& m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 \\
& v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
& v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} \Big) / \\
& \left((8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \right. \\
& \left. (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \\
& \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4) \right) + \\
& (4. q (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} \\
 & \quad m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} \\
 & \quad m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
 & \quad v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) / \\
 & \left((8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \right. \\
 & \left. (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)^2 \right) / \\
 & \left(\sqrt{\left(\frac{0.25 q^2 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)^2}{(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)^2} - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. (0.666667 (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - \right. \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
 & \quad v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) / \\
 & \left((8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \right. \\
 & \quad (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \right) + (0.419974 \\
 & \quad (-3. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & \quad (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 & \quad (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
 & \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
 & \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - \\
 & \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + \\
 & \quad 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
 & \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & \quad 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 + \\
 12. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} \Big) \Big/ \\
& \left((0. + 0. i) + 1.43146 \times 10^8 \cos[2. \beta] \right)^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - \right. \\
& \quad \left. 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \\
& \left(27. q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \right. \\
& \quad \left(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4 \right) \\
& \quad \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \right. \\
& \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
& \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
& \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
& \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& \quad 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& \quad 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& \quad 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& \quad 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& \quad 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& \quad 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& \quad 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& \quad 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& \quad 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& \quad \left. 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \right)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 - 9. q^2 \\
 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 & (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) + \\
 2. & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^3 + 27. q^2 \\
 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^8 \\
 & (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)^2 \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 72. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sqrt{\left(-4 \cdot \left(-3 \cdot q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1 \cdot v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right.\right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left.\left. v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2\right)^4 \left(-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \right.\right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left.\left. \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4\right) \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.06262 \times 10^{35} \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. m^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. v^6 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. q^2 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.60437 \times 10^{86} \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. m^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 7.14043 \times 10^{69} \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. m^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. q^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. v^4 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. m^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left. v^6 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \right.\right.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 9.01595 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.58896 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times \\
& 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times \\
& 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
 & v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} \\
 & v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times \\
 & 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
 & v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} \\
 & q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.42809 \times \\
 & 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} \\
 & v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 + \\
 12. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} \\
 & m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} \\
& v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} \\
& m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times \\
& 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} \\
& m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} \\
& m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
& m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
& m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} \Big)^3 + \\
& \left(27. q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \left(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 \right) \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.73742 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
 & v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
 & v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} \\
 & q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
 & v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.62868 \times 10^{53} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.2081 \times \\
 & 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
 & v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.61816 \times 10^{69} \\
 & m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 9.01595 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \\
 & v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} \\
 & q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.52058 \times \\
 & 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 - \\
9. q^2 (& 8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \\
& q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.06262 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.73742 \times \\
& 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.36964 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} \\
 & q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
 & v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times \\
 & 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} \\
 & v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 \\
 & v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times \\
 & 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times \\
 & 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times \\
 & 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times \\
& 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times \\
& 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times \\
& 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.76796 \times \\
& 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + 2. (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times \\
& 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times \\
& 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} \\
& q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.42809 \times \\
& 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^3 + \\
27. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^8 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)^2 \\
(1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
& m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
& q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} \\
& v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} \\
 & m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
 & q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} \\
 & v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 \\
 & v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.36964 \times \\
 & 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times \\
 & 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times \\
 & 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} \\
 & q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times \\
& 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 \\
& v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times \\
& 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} \\
& m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} \\
& m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} \\
& q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times \\
& 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
72. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) (2.67396 \times 10^{84} \text{m}^2 + \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} \text{q}^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \text{m}^2 \text{v}^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} \\
& \text{q}^2 \text{v}^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \text{m}^2 \text{v}^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} \text{q}^2 \text{v}^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \text{m}^2 \text{v}^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \text{q}^2 \text{v}^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& \text{m}^2 \text{v}^8 + 1.22945 \times 10^{17} \text{q}^2 \text{v}^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \text{z}^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \text{v}^2 \text{z}^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \text{v}^4 \text{z}^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& \text{v}^6 \text{z}^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \text{v}^8 \text{z}^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} \text{m}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 6.4175 \times 10^{85} \text{q}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} \text{m}^2 \text{v}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.85617 \times 10^{69} \text{q}^2 \text{v}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} \text{m}^2 \text{v}^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} \text{q}^2 \text{v}^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} \\
& \text{m}^2 \text{v}^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} \text{q}^2 \text{v}^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times \\
& 10^{17} \text{m}^2 \text{v}^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} \text{q}^2 \text{v}^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} \text{z}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} \text{v}^2 \text{z}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} \text{v}^4 \text{z}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} \text{v}^6 \text{z}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} \text{v}^8 \text{z}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} \text{m}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} \text{q}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} \text{m}^2 \text{v}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} \text{q}^2 \text{v}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \text{m}^2 \text{v}^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} \text{q}^2 \text{v}^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
& \text{m}^2 \text{v}^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.14917 \times 10^{36} \text{q}^2 \text{v}^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times \\
& 10^{17} \text{m}^2 \text{v}^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} \text{q}^2 \text{v}^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} \text{z}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} \text{v}^2 \text{z}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \text{v}^4 \text{z}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \text{v}^6 \text{z}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \text{v}^8 \text{z}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} \text{m}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.52962 \times 10^{86} \text{q}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} \text{m}^2 \text{v}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} \text{q}^2 \text{v}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} \text{m}^2 \text{v}^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} \text{q}^2 \text{v}^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} \\
& \text{m}^2 \text{v}^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} \text{q}^2 \text{v}^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times \\
& 10^{18} \text{m}^2 \text{v}^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} \text{q}^2 \text{v}^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} \text{z}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} \text{v}^2 \text{z}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \text{v}^4 \text{z}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \text{v}^6 \text{z}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \text{v}^8 \text{z}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} \text{m}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} \text{q}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} \text{m}^2 \text{v}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} \text{q}^2 \text{v}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} \text{m}^2 \text{v}^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} \text{q}^2 \text{v}^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} \\
& \text{m}^2 \text{v}^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.81216 \times 10^{36} \text{q}^2 \text{v}^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times \\
& 10^{18} \text{m}^2 \text{v}^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} \text{q}^2 \text{v}^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} \text{z}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} \text{v}^2 \text{z}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} \text{v}^4 \text{z}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} \text{v}^6 \text{z}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} \text{v}^8 \text{z}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} \text{m}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} \text{q}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} \text{m}^2 \text{v}^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} \text{q}^2 \text{v}^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} \\
& \text{m}^2 \text{v}^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} \text{q}^2 \text{v}^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times \\
& 10^{35} \text{m}^2 \text{v}^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} \text{q}^2 \text{v}^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.76796 \times \\
& 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} \left(1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + \right. \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
& m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
& q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} \\
& v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 \\
& v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.36964 \times \\
& 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times \\
& 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times \\
& 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times \\
& 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 \\
& v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times \\
& 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} \\
& m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} \\
& m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} \\
& q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times \\
& 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left. \left. \left. \left. \left. v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} \right)^2 \right)^{1/3} \right) + \\
 & \left(0.264567 \left(27. q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \left(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4 \right) \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \right. \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 - 9. q^2 \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
& (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
2. & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^3 + 27. q^2 \\
 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^8 \\
 & (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)^2 \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) - \\
72. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & \sqrt{\left(-4. \left(-3. q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16}\right.\right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left.\left.\text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2\right)^4 \left(-8.19632 \times 10^{16} +\right.\right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left.\left.3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4\right)\right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 +\right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left.2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 -\right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left.3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34}\right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left.m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 -\right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left.8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68}\right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left.v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 +\right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left.8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 +\right.\right.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.06262 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.34792 \times 10^{85} \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.9724 \times \\
& 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times \\
& 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 9.01595 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.58896 \times 10^{52} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 \\
 & z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) + \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
 & v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times \\
 & 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} \\
 & v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times \\
 & 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
 & v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
 & v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times \\
& 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} \\
& q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.42809 \times \\
& 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 + \\
12. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} \\
& m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} \\
& v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} \\
& m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} \\
& m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times \\
& 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} \\
& m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} \\
 & m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
 & m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
 & m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} \\
 & q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
 & v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} \Big)^3 + \\
 & \left(27. q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \left(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 \right) \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.73742 \times 10^{17} \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} \right. \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} \\
& q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.62868 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.2081 \times \\
& 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.61816 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 9.01595 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} \\
& q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.52058 \times \\
& 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 - \\
& 9. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
 & q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.06262 \times 10^{35} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.73742 \times \\
 & 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 \\
 & z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
 & v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
 & v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.36964 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} \\
& q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
& v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times \\
& 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 \\
& v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times \\
& 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times \\
& 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times \\
& 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times \\
& 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times \\
 & 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} \\
 & q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
 & v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times \\
 & 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} \\
 & v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
 2. & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
 & v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times \\
 & 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} \\
 & v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times \\
 & 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times \\
& 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} \\
& q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.42809 \times \\
& 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^3 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 27. \ q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. \ v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^8 \left(-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \right. \\
 & \quad \left. 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4 \right)^2 \\
 & \left(1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + \right. \\
 & \quad 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
 & \quad m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + \\
 & \quad 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
 & \quad m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
 & \quad 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
 & \quad 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
 & \quad q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
 & \quad 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
 & \quad 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
 & \quad 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} \\
 & \quad v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
 & \quad 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \\
 & \quad \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} \\
 & \quad m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
 & \quad \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} \\
 & \quad m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
 & \quad \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} \\
 & \quad m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 \\
 & \quad v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} \\
 & \quad m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
 & \quad \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
 & \quad v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
 & \quad \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \\
 & \quad m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
 & \quad \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} \\
 & \quad m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times \\
& 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 \\
 & v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
 & q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
 & v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
 & v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} \\
 & m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} \\
 & q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times \\
 & 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
 & v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 72. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} \\
 & q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& m^2 v^8 + 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times \\
& 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times \\
& 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times \\
& 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times \\
& 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} \\
 & v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} \\
 & q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
 & q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} \\
 & v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 \\
 & v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
 & v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times \\
 & 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \\
 & \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} \\
 & v^4 z^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \\
 & \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \\
 & \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^4 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 \\
 & v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
 & \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 v^2 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
 & q^2 v^4 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
 & v^8 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
 & \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
 & v^6 z^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \\
 & \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} \\
 & m^4 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \\
 & \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} \\
 & q^4 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \\
 & \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \\
 & \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times \\
 & 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \\
 & \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
 & v^6 z^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} \Big)^2 \Big)^{1/3} \Big) /
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \\
& \quad \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} \\
& \quad m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
& \quad v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} \\
& \quad q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.14917 \times 10^{36} \\
& \quad q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} \\
& \quad q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 \\
& \quad z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
& \quad v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \\
& \quad v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \\
& \quad \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} \\
& \quad m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
& \quad v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} \\
& \quad q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} \\
& \quad q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} \\
& \quad q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 \\
& \quad z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
& \quad v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \\
& \quad v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \\
& \quad \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} \\
& \quad m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
& \quad v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} \\
& \quad q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.81216 \times 10^{36} \\
& \quad q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} \\
& \quad q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 \\
& \quad z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} \\
& \quad v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} \\
& m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. \\
& v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} \Big) \Big/ \\
& \left((8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \right. \\
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
& \left. \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 \Big) \Big) + \\
& (0.419974 (-3. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
& (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 + \\
 12. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left(\left(\left(1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \right. \right. \right. \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& \left. \left. \left. 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} \right) \right) \right) / \\
& \left(\left((0. + 0. i) + 1.43146 \times 10^8 \cos[2. \beta] \right)^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \right. \\
& \left(27. q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \right. \\
& \left(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \right. \\
& \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4 \right) \\
& \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \right. \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& \left. \left. \left. 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \right. \right. \right.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 - 9. q^2 \\
 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 & (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} \\
& \quad q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
& \quad v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
& \quad v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} \\
& \quad m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
& \quad z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} \\
& \quad q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2. \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& \quad 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& \quad 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& \quad 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& \quad 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& \quad 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& \quad 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^3 + 27. q^2 \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^8 \\
& (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)^2 \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
 & \quad z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) - 72. \\
 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & \quad 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & \quad 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} \\
& \quad q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} \\
& \quad q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} \\
& \quad q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} \\
& \quad q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
& \quad z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) + \\
 & \sqrt{(-4. (-3. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - \\
 & \quad 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - \\
 & \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
 & \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
 & \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
 & \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & \quad 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & \quad 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & \quad 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & \quad 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & \quad 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & \quad 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & \quad 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & \quad 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & \quad 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & \quad 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & \quad 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 + 12. \\
 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
 & q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \\
 & z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} \\
 & m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
 & q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
 & q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
 & v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
 & q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
 & v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 \\
 & v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 \\
& z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} \Big)^3 + \\
(27. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - \\
8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + \\
5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 - \\
 9. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) + \\
 2. & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^3 + \\
27. & q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^8 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4)^2 \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 \\
 & v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
& v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 \\
 & \quad v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 \\
 & \quad v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) - \\
 72. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 \\
& \quad v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
& v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} \Big) \Big) \Big) \Big) \Big) \Big)^{1/3} \Big) +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left(0.264567 \left(27. q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \quad \left. \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 \right) \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - \\
 & \quad \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
 & \quad \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
 & \quad \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \\
 & \quad \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
 & \quad \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & \quad \quad 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad \quad 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad \quad 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad \quad 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad \quad 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad \quad 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad \quad 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad \quad 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad \quad 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad \quad 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad \quad 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad \quad 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad \quad 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad \quad 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad \quad 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & \quad \quad 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad \quad 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & \quad \quad 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad \quad 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & \quad \quad 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & \quad \quad 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & \quad \quad 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & \quad \quad 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & \quad \quad 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & \quad \quad 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & \quad \quad 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & \quad \quad 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & \quad \quad 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 - 9. q^2 \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
& (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2. \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^3 + 27. q^2 \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^8 \\
& (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4)^2 \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
 & v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
 & z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
 & v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
 & v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
 & z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) - 72. \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} \\
& \quad q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} \\
& \quad q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} \\
& \quad q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
 & \quad z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & \sqrt{\left(-4. \left(-3. q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \right.\right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left.\left. v^2 \sin[\beta]^2\right)^4 \left(-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - \right.\right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left.\left. 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4\right) \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - \right.\right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left.\left. 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - \right.\right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left.\left. 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \right.\right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left.\left. 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \right.\right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left.\left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \right.\right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left.\left. 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \right.\right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left.\left. 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \right.\right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left.\left. 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \right.\right.\right. \\
 & \quad \left.\left.\left. 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \right.\right.\right.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 + 12. \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
 & q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
 & v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 \\
 & v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
& q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
& v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
& q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 \\
& z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} \Big)^3 + \\
(27. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - \\
8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + \\
5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 - \\
 & 9. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
& (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
2. & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^3 + \\
 27. & q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^8 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)^2 \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 \\
& \quad v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
 & \quad v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
 & \quad \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
 & \quad q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 \\
 & \quad v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 \\
 & \quad v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
72. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 \\
 & v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
 & q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} \Big)^{1/3} \Big) / \\
 & \left(\left((0. + 0. i) + 1.43146 \times 10^8 \text{Cos}[2. \beta] \right)^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \right) + \\
 & 0.5 \sqrt{\left(\frac{0.5 q^2 \left(-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 \right)^2}{\left(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 \right)^2} - \right.} \\
 & \left. (1.33333 \right. \\
 & \left. (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + \right. \\
 & \left. 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - \right. \\
 & \left. 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \right. \\
 & \left. 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + \right. \\
 & \left. 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \right. \\
 & \left. 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \\
& \quad \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \\
& \quad \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
& \quad v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} \\
& \quad q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} \\
& \quad q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} \\
& \quad q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} \\
& \quad q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 \\
& \quad z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} \\
& \quad v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} \\
& \quad v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \\
& \quad \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} \\
& \quad m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
& \quad v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} \\
& \quad q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.14917 \times 10^{36} \\
& \quad q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} \\
& \quad q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 \\
& \quad z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
& \quad v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \\
& \quad v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \\
& \quad \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} \\
& \quad m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} \\
& q^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} \\
& q^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 \\
& z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \\
& v^8 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \\
& \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
& v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.81216 \times 10^{36} \\
& q^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} \\
& q^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 \\
& z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} \\
& v^4 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} \\
& v^8 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \\
& \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \\
& \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
& z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& v^8 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \\
& \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} \\
& m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. \\
& v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} \Big) / \\
& \left((8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \right. \\
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \Big) - \\
& (0.419974 (-3. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
& (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 + \\
12. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} \Big) \Big) / \\
 & \left(((0. + 0. i) + 1.43146 \times 10^8 \text{Cos}[2. \beta])^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \right. \\
 & \left(27. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \right. \\
 & \quad \left(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \\
 & \quad \quad \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 \right) \\
 & \quad \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \right. \\
 & \quad \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - \\
 & \quad \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
 & \quad \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
 & \quad \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \\
 & \quad \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
 & \quad \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & \quad \quad 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad \quad 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad \quad 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad \quad \left. \left. 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 - 9. q^2 \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
& (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
& \quad z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} \\
& \quad q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} \\
& \quad q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} \\
& \quad q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} \\
& \quad m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) + 2. \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^3 + 27. q^2 \\
 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^8 \\
 & (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)^2 \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
& \quad z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) - 72. \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& \quad 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& \quad 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& \quad 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& \quad 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& \quad 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& \quad 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& \quad 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} \\
 & q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
& v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
& z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) + \\
 & \sqrt{(-4. (-3. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - \\
 & \quad 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - \\
 & \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
 & \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
 & \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
 & \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & \quad 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 + 12. \\
 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} \\
& m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
& q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
& v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
& \quad q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \\
& \quad \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
& \quad m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
& \quad v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 \\
& \quad v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 \\
& \quad z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} \Big)^3 + \\
(27. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - \\
8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + \\
5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 - \\
 9. & q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
 & (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
2. & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^3 + \\
 27. & q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^8 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4)^2 \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 \\
 & v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
 & q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 \\
 & v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 \\
 & v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) - \\
 72. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
& v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} \Big) \Big) \Big) \Big) \Big)^{1/3} - \\
 & \left(0.264567 \left(27. q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 \right) \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \right. \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 - 9. q^2 \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
& (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} \\
 & \quad m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
 & \quad v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + 2. \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & \quad 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & \quad 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
 & \quad 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & \quad 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
 & \quad 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
 & \quad 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^3 + 27. q^2 \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^8
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4)^2 \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + \\
 & \quad 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
 & \quad 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
 & \quad 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - \\
 & \quad 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
 & \quad 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
 & \quad 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
 & \quad 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
 & \quad 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
 & \quad 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
 & \quad 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
 & \quad 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
 & \quad 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
 & \quad 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
 & \quad v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
 & \quad \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
 & \quad z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
 & \quad v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
& z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) - 72. \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} \\
 & \quad m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
 & \quad v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & \quad 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & \quad 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + \\
 & \quad 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
 & \quad 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & \quad 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + \\
 & \quad 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
 & \quad 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
 & \quad 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
& \quad z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & \sqrt{\left(-4. \left(-3. q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \left(-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 \right) \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \right. \right. \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 + 12. \\
 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
 & q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} \\
& m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
& q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
& q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 \\
& \quad z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} \Big)^3 + \\
(27. & q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
& (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
& \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
& \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - \\
& \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + \\
& \quad 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
& \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& \quad 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& \quad 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& \quad 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& \quad 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& \quad 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& \quad 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& \quad 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& \quad 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& \quad 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& \quad 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& \quad 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& \quad 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& \quad 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& \quad 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& \quad 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& \quad 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& \quad 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& \quad 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} \Big)^2 - \\
 9. & q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \right. \\
 & \left. v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \left(-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \right. \\
 & \left. 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4 \right) \\
 & \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \right. \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
 2. & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^3 + \\
27. & q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^8 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4)^2 \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 \\
 & v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 \\
 & v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 \\
 & v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 72. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left((0. + 0. i) + 1.43146 \times 10^8 \cos[2. \beta] \right)^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - \right. \\
 & \quad \left. 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^4 + \\
 & \left(0.25 \left(- \frac{1. q^3 \left(-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4 \right)^3}{\left(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4 \right)^3} - \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left(8. q \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - \\
 & \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
 & \quad 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - \\
 & \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + \\
 & \quad 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
 & \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + \\
 & \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.06262 \times 10^{35} \\
 & \quad m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} \\
 & \quad q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \\
 & \quad v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & \quad 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & \quad 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} \\
 & \quad q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & \quad 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & \quad 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \\
 & \quad v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & \quad 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & \quad 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & \quad 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & \quad 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) / \\
& \left((8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \right. \\
& \left. (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \right. \\
& \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) \right) + \\
& (4. q (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
& v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} \Big) / \\
& \left((8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \right. \\
& \left. (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4)^2 \right) \Big) / \\
& \left(\sqrt{\left(\frac{0.25 q^2 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4)^2}{(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4)^2} \right.} \right. \\
& \left. (0.666667 (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - \right. \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} \\
 & m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
 & v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) / \\
 & \left((8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \right. \\
 & \left. (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \\
 & \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \right) + (0.419974 \\
 & (-3. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 + \\
12. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} \Big) \Big) / \\
& \left((0. + 0. i) + 1.43146 \times 10^8 \cos[2. \beta] \right)^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - \right. \\
& \left. 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \\
& \left(27. q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \right. \\
& \left(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4 \right) \\
& \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \right. \\
& \left. 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \right. \\
& \left. 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \right.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 - 9. q^2 \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
& (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.9862 \times \\
& 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& \beta)^4 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.17864 \times 10^{35} \\
 & \quad q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
2. & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^3 + 27. q^2 \\
 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^8 \\
 & (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4)^2 \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
72. & \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \\
& \left(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 \right) \\
& \left(2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \right. \\
& \quad 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - \\
& \quad 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& \quad 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - \\
& \quad 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& \quad 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& \quad 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& \quad 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& \quad 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& \quad 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& \quad 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& \quad 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& \quad 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& \quad 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& \quad 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& \quad 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& \quad 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& \quad 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& \quad 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& \quad 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& \quad 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& \quad 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& \quad 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& \quad 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& \quad 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& \quad 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& \quad 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& \quad 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& \quad 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& \quad 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& \quad 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& \quad 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& \quad 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& \quad 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & \sqrt{\left(-4. \left(-3. q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2\right)^4 \left(-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4\right) \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.06262 \times 10^{35} \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \right. \right. \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.60437 \times 10^{86} \\
& m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 7.14043 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} \\
& q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 9.01595 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.58896 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times \\
& 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times \\
& 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times \\
& 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} \\
& q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.42809 \times \\
& 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 + \\
12. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} \\
& m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} \\
& v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} \\
& m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} \\
& m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times \\
& 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} \\
& q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} \\
& m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 \\
& v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
& m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
 & m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} \\
 & q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
 & v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} \Big)^3 + \\
 & \left(27. q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \left(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4 \Big) \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - \right. \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \\
 & q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} \\
 & v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times \\
 & 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.73742 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
 & v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
 & v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} \\
 & q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.62868 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times \\
& 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.24125 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} \\
& q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.58896 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 - \\
& 9. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} + \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
& (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.06262 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 9.01595 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.58896 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) \\
& (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 9.28256 \times 10^{69} \\
& q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} \\
& q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.81216 \times 10^{36} \\
 & \quad q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \\
 & \quad \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} \\
 & \quad v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \\
 & \quad \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} \\
 & \quad m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} \\
 & \quad q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} \\
 & \quad m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \\
 & \quad \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & \quad v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
 & \quad \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} \\
 & \quad q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
 & \quad m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 \\
 & \quad z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
 2. & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
 & \quad m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & \quad 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
 & \quad 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & \quad 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
 & \quad v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - \\
 & \quad 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} \\
 & \quad m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} \\
 & \quad q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & \quad 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \\
 & \quad \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} \\
 & \quad v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & \quad 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \\
 & \quad \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} \\
 & \quad m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & \quad 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^3 + \\
 27. q^2 & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^8 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)^2 \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} \\
 & m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 \\
 & v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} \\
 & m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} \\
 & q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 \\
 & v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} \\
 & q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} \\
 & v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
 & q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
 & q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} \\
& q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} \\
& z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} \\
& q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.36964 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 9.01595 \times 10^{17} \\
& q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} \\
& q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.07171 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 8.40123 \times 10^{17} \\
& q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} \\
& m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 \\
& v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 \\
& v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 \\
& v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 \\
& v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} \\
& m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} \\
& v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} \\
& m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 \\
& v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 \\
& v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 \\
& v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
& m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12}) - \\
72. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} \\
& q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} \\
& q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.81216 \times 10^{36} \\
 & q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} \\
 & v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} \\
 & m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
 & v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
 & v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} \\
& q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} \\
& q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} \\
& q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} \\
& q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 \\
& z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} \\
& v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.47615 \times 10^{85} \\
& q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} \\
& q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.58206 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.32761 \times 10^{17} \\
& q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 \\
& z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} \\
& v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.88271 \times 10^{85} \\
& q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} \\
& q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.36964 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} \\
 & q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 9.01595 \times 10^{17} \\
 & q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
 & v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
 & v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 \\
 & z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \\
 & v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
 & q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
 & q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} \\
 & q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} \\
 & q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} \\
 & z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
 & v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} \\
 & m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
 & q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 \\
 & v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 \\
 & v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 \\
 & z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 \\
 & v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 \\
 & z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} \\
 & q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 \\
 & v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 \\
 & v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 \\
 & z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
 & v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 \\
 & v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 \\
 & z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
 & v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 \\
 & v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \\
& \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 \\
& v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 \\
& v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \\
& \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.22758 \times 10^{19} \\
& v^6 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 - 9. q^2 \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
& (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4) (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \\
& 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} \\
& q^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
& v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 \\
& v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \\
& \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \\
& \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 \\
& v^6 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \\
& \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 \\
& z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^6 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19172 \times 10^{53} \\
 & m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 \\
 & v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 9.75859 \times 10^{69} \\
 & q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 \\
 & v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 \\
 & v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
 & v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
 & v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 9.01595 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
 & v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.58896 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
 & v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
 & v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} \\
& \quad q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 \\
& \quad v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 \\
& \quad v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} \\
& \quad v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \\
& \quad m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 \\
& \quad v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \\
& \quad \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \\
& \quad \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} \\
& \quad q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 \\
& \quad v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 \\
& \quad v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 \\
& \quad z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& \quad v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 \\
& \quad v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 \\
& \quad v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \\
& \quad \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 \\
& \quad z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \\
& \quad \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 \\
& \quad v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
 & v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 \\
 & z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
 & v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 \\
 & v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) + \\
 2. & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
 & v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 \\
 & v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 \\
& v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 \\
& v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} \\
& q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
& v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 \\
& v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 \\
& v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 \\
& v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^3 + 27. q^2 \\
& (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^8 \\
& (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4)^2 \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 \\
& v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 \\
& v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 \\
& v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 \\
& z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.47615 \times 10^{85} \\
& q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} \\
& q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 \\
& v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.32761 \times 10^{17} \\
& q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
& v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} \\
& q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 \\
& v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 9.01595 \times 10^{17} \\
& q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 \\
& z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} \\
& q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 \\
& v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 8.40123 \times 10^{17} \\
& q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \\
& q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 \\
& v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 \\
 & v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 \\
 & q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 \\
 & v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
 & v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 \\
 & v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} \\
 & z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
 & z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \\
 & q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 \\
 & v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 \\
 & v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 \\
 & v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 \\
 & v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 \\
 & v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 \\
 & v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 \\
 & z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 72. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 \\
 & (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - \\
& 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} \\
& \quad q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 3.53591 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
& \quad v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
& \quad z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} \\
& \quad q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
& \quad v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 \\
& \quad z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} \\
& \quad q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 \\
& \quad v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 \\
& \quad v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 \\
& \quad z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} \\
& \quad m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 \\
& \quad v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} \\
& \quad v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \\
& \quad \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} q^2 \\
& \quad v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
 & v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 \\
 & z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
 & v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 \\
 & v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
 & q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 \\
 & v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 \\
 & q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
 & q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 \\
 & z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
 & v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} \\
& z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
& z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.54709 \times 10^{69} \\
& q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 \\
& v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.91529 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.32761 \times 10^{17} \\
& q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
& v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} \\
& q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 \\
& v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 9.01595 \times 10^{17} \\
& q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
& v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 \\
& z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} \\
 & q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 \\
 & v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} \\
 & q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 8.40123 \times 10^{17} \\
 & q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 \\
 & v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
 & v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 \\
 & v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 \\
 & v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 \\
 & v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 \\
 & v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 \\
 & z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} q^2 \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 \\
& z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& \sqrt{\left(-4. \left(-3. q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2\right)^4 \left(-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4\right) \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.73742 \times 10^{17} \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \right. \right. \right.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
 & v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.62868 \times 10^{53} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
 & v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 2.61816 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 9.01595 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{10} - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} \\
 & v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.58896 \times 10^{52} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
 & v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} \\
& v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
 & v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} \\
 & v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^2 + \\
 12. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) \\
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
 & q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} \\
 & q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} \\
& q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} \\
& z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} \\
& m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} \\
& q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \\
& q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
& q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} \\
& q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} \\
& z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.10497 \times 10^{35} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 4.01094 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} \\
& q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} \\
& q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} \\
& z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.48965 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} \\
& m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} \\
& m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} \\
& v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} \\
& m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 \\
& v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
& m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
& m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
& v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} \Big)^3 + \\
& \left(27. q^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \left(2.04908 \times 10^{16} - \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4 \right) \right. \\
& \left. \left(-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. v^2 z^2 + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 2.78068 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 2.35728 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.73742 \times 10^{17} \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 6.18837 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. \sin[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.03282 \times 10^{53} \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.63926 \times 10^{18} \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \right. \right.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} \\
 & q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.74786 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
 & v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.62868 \times 10^{53} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{18} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.36049 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} \\
 & v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \\
 & v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.61816 \times 10^{69} \\
 & m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 9.01595 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \\
 & v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
 & v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.58896 \times 10^{52} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} \\
 & v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12})^2 - \\
 & 9. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)^4 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
 & 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \\
 & (-5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 - 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^2 +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 - \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 + \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 - \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 + 3.74354 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 4.27833 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.6661 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.90412 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.78068 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.17792 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.06262 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.35728 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.73742 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
& 6.55706 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 \\
& z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.39046 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 4.76029 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 6.18837 \times 10^{69} \\
& q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 7.9448 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.03282 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.89319 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 7.66115 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.63926 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.13104 \times 10^{18} \\
& q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.60437 \times 10^{86} m^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.35308 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 7.14043 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.04726 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19172 \times 10^{53} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.74786 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.83978 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.2965 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.4589 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.60638 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 5.34792 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 3.9724 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \\
& \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.94659 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.33698 \times 10^{86} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.19265 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 9.75859 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.62868 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.2081 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.36049 \times 10^{18} \\
& q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.88271 \times 10^{85} m^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.06958 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.61816 \times 10^{69} \\
 & m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.76029 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 7.9448 \times 10^{52} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 3.24125 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 9.01595 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.63926 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.38014 \times 10^{68} v^2 \\
 & z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 3.9724 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
 & v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.06958 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.13917 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
 & v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.52058 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.58896 \times 10^{52} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.17864 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.87333 \times 10^{69} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.13733 \times 10^{53} v^2 \\
 & z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.73839 \times 10^{36} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.22758 \times 10^{19} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 34. v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12}) \\
 & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
 & v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} \\
 & q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} \\
 & v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 \\
 & v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} \\
 & q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
 & \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.81216 \times 10^{36} \\
& q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
& v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12}) + \\
2. & (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 - 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
& 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
& 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} \\
& q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.08569 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.14917 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.62178 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} \\
& v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.81216 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} \\
& m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})^3 + \\
& 27. q^2 (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \\
& \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^8 (-8.19632 \times 10^{16} + \\
& 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^2 - 3.27853 \times 10^{17} \sin[\beta]^4)^2 \\
& (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
& 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
& 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.76029 \times 10^{68} \\
& q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.9448 \times 10^{51} \\
& q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 5.89319 \times 10^{34} \\
& q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
& 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.63926 \times 10^{17} \\
& q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
& 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 \\
 & v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.4589 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} \\
 & v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.00547 \times 10^{85} m^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} \\
 & m^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
 & m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} \\
 & m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} \\
 & q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} \\
 & m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \\
 & q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} \\
 & v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} \\
 & m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 \\
 & v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 \\
 & v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 \\
 & v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} \\
 & m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} \\
 & q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
 & m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^6 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} \\
& m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 \\
& v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} \\
& m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} \\
& q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} \\
& q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} \\
& m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 \\
& v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 \\
& v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 \\
& v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 \\
& v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} \\
& m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} \\
& v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & m^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 \\
 & v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 \\
 & v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 \\
 & v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} \\
 & m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
 & m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} \\
 & q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
 & m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \\
 & \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} \\
 & v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
 72. & (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & v^2 \sin[\beta]^2)^4 (2.04908 \times 10^{16} - 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^4) (2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 + \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} q^2 - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 - \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 + \\
 & 5.9586 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 - \\
 & 4.41989 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 + \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
 & v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 6.4175 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.85617 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 - 4.76688 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 + 3.53591 \times 10^{35} \\
 & q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 9.83559 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 \\
 & z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.08569 \times 10^{86} \\
 & q^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 9.28256 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.54924 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.14917 \times 10^{36}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.19657 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 3.52962 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.57089 \times 10^{70} \\
& q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.62178 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.94475 \times 10^{36} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.40957 \times 10^{18} \\
& q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.28897 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 1.46379 \times 10^{70} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 2.44303 \times 10^{53} q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.81216 \times 10^{36} \\
& q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.04074 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} z^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 9.931 \times 10^{51} \\
& v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.04908 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 \\
& \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.60437 \times 10^{86} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} \\
& m^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 7.14043 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19172 \times 10^{53} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 8.83978 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 2.4589 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{84} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} v^2 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{10} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.20875 \times 10^{85} q^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 \\
& v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 1.42809 \times 10^{69} q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 2.38344 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 1.76796 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 4.91779 \times 10^{17} q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.43667 \times 10^{69} z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} v^2 \\
& z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 8.69196 \times 10^{35} v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 6.13791 \times 10^{18} v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 17. v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (1.33698 \times 10^{84} m^4 + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 + \\
 & 1.33698 \times 10^{84} q^4 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 v^2 - \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} q^4 v^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 v^4 + 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{50} q^4 v^4 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 v^6 - \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} q^4 v^6 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} m^4 v^8 + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 + \\
 & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} m^2 z^2 - \\
 & 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 + 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 + \\
 & 1.19007 \times 10^{68} q^2 v^2 z^2 - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 - \\
 & 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} m^2 v^6 z^2 + \\
 & 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 - 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 - \\
 & 4.09816 \times 10^{16} q^2 v^8 z^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 - \\
 & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 z^4 - \\
 & 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 - \\
 & 8.02187 \times 10^{84} m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.87177 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.06958 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 \\
 & v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8.3305 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 4.76029 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 \\
 & v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.39034 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.9448 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 \\
 & v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.03131 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 5.89319 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} \\
 & m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2.86871 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.63926 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} \\
 & m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.95036 \times 10^{68} \\
 & q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} m^2 \\
 & v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.04908 \times 10^{17} \\
 & q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \\
 & 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} \\
 & v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - \\
 & 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} \\
 & m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 3.47615 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 \\
 & v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.54709 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} \\
 & m^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + \\
 & 2.58206 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
 & m^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 - \\
 & 1.91529 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 5.32761 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} \\
& m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} \\
& q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \\
& q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^4 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^4 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} \\
& m^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 8.02187 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 5.88271 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.19007 \times 10^{69} m^4 \\
& v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.57022 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 2.61816 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} m^4 \\
& v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 5.9586 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.36964 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} m^4 \\
& v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.41989 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 3.24125 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^6 - 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.22945 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 9.01595 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^6 + 5.34792 \times 10^{85} \\
& m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.19007 \times 10^{69} \\
& q^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 3.9724 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^2 v^4 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.94659 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^6 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 + 4.09816 \times 10^{17} \\
& q^2 v^8 z^2 \sin[\beta]^6 - 2.67396 \times 10^{85} z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - 1.9862 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 1.4733 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^6 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} \\
& m^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 6.6849 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 5.48161 \times 10^{85} q^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 8.92554 \times 10^{68} m^4 \\
& v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 2.97518 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 2.43965 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} \\
& m^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + 4.9655 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 4.07171 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} \\
& m^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - 3.68324 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 - \\
& 3.02026 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \sin[\beta]^8 + 3.07362 \times 10^{17} \\
& m^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + 1.02454 \times 10^{18} m^2 q^2 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 8.40123 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \sin[\beta]^8 - 4.01094 \times 10^{85} \\
& m^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 - 1.33698 \times 10^{85} q^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + \\
& 1.78511 \times 10^{69} m^2 v^2 z^2 \sin[\beta]^8 + 5.95036 \times 10^{68}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.9793 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 9.931 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.20995 \times 10^{35} m^2 \\
& v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 7.36649 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 6.14724 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 2.04908 \times 10^{17} \\
& q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 2.00547 \times 10^{85} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - \\
& 8.92554 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + 1.48965 \times 10^{52} \\
& v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 1.10497 \times 10^{35} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 + \\
& 3.07362 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^8 - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} \\
& m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.94135 \times 10^{85} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 2.67396 \times 10^{85} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 3.57022 \times 10^{68} m^4 \\
& v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.30908 \times 10^{69} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{69} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} m^4 \\
& v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 2.18482 \times 10^{52} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{52} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} m^4 \\
& v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.62063 \times 10^{35} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.4733 \times 10^{35} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.22945 \times 10^{17} m^4 \\
& v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 4.50798 \times 10^{17} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{17} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.60437 \times 10^{85} \\
& m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 2.67396 \times 10^{84} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 7.14043 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.19007 \times 10^{68} \\
& q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.19172 \times 10^{52} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 1.9862 \times 10^{51} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.83978 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 1.4733 \times 10^{34} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 2.4589 \times 10^{17} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.09816 \times 10^{16} \\
& q^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 8.02187 \times 10^{84} z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + \\
& 3.57022 \times 10^{68} v^2 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - 5.9586 \times 10^{51} \\
& v^4 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 4.41989 \times 10^{34} v^6 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} - \\
& 1.22945 \times 10^{17} v^8 z^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{10} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} \\
& m^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 5.34792 \times 10^{84} m^2 q^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 5.34792 \times 10^{84} q^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.95036 \times 10^{67} m^4 \\
& v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.38014 \times 10^{68} m^2 q^2 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.38014 \times 10^{68} q^4 v^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} m^4 \\
& v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 3.9724 \times 10^{51} m^2 q^2 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 3.9724 \times 10^{51} q^4 v^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} m^4 \\
& v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.94659 \times 10^{34} m^2 q^2 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 2.94659 \times 10^{34} q^4 v^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 2.04908 \times 10^{16} \\
& m^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 8.19632 \times 10^{16} m^2 q^2 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.19632 \times 10^{16} q^4 v^8 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 2.67396 \times 10^{84} \\
& m^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.43667 \times 10^{69} q^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 1.19007 \times 10^{68} m^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 5.68665 \times 10^{52} \\
& q^2 v^2 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 1.9862 \times 10^{51} m^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + \\
& 8.69196 \times 10^{35} q^2 v^4 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 1.4733 \times 10^{34} \\
& m^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - 6.13791 \times 10^{18} q^2 v^6 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} - \\
& 4.09816 \times 10^{16} m^2 v^8 z^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^{12} + 17. q^2 v^8
\end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{\begin{aligned} & z^2 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 1.33698 \times 10^{84} z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - \\ & 5.95036 \times 10^{67} v^2 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + 9.931 \times 10^{50} v^4 \\ & z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} - 7.36649 \times 10^{33} v^6 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} + \\ & 2.04908 \times 10^{16} v^8 z^4 \sin[\beta]^{12} \end{aligned}}{\left(\left((0. + 0. i) + 1.43146 \times 10^8 \cos[2. \beta] \right)^2 \left(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^4 \right) \left. \right. \left. \right\}}^{1/3}$$